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The SatisFactory project consortium is composed of:		
CERTH¹	Centre for Research and Technology Hellas	Greece
SIGMA²	Sigma Orionis SA	France
FIT	Fraunhofer-Gesellschaft zur Foerderung der Angewandten Forschung E.V	Germany
COMAU	Comau SPA	Italy
EPFL	École Polytechnique Fédérale de Lausanne	Switzerland
ISMB	Istituto Superiore Mario Boella sulle tecnologie dell'informazione e delle telecomunicazioni	Italy
ABE	Atlantis Engineering AE	Greece
REGOLA	Regola srl	Italy
SUNLIGHT	Systems Sunlight Industrial & Commercial Company of Defensive, Energy, Electronic and Telecommunication Systems S.A.	Greece
GlassUP	GlassUp srl	Italy
QPLAN	Q-PLAN International Advisors LTD	Greece

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1 Project Coordinator

²Terminated beneficiary since June 2016 and replaced by QPLAN

AUTHORS LIST

Leading Author (Editor)				
Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email	
Tsakiris	Athanasios	CERTH	atsakir@iti.gr	
Co-authors				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Antoniou	Maria	ATLANTIS	antoniou@abe.gr
2	Bergamaschi	Luca	COMAU	luca.bergamaschi@comau.com
3	Cultrona	Pietro	COMAU	pietro.cultrona@comau.com
4	Dontsiou	Maria	ATLANTIS	dontsiou@abe.gr
5	Kanidis	Stefanos	SUNLIGHT	s.kanidis@sunlight.gr
6	Krinidis	Stelios	CERTH	krinidis@iti.gr
7	Lithoxidou	Eirini	CERTH	elithoxo@iti.gr
8	Matonaki	Anastasia	Q-PLAN	matonaki@qplan.gr
9	Parcharidis	Symeon	SUNLIGHT	s.parcharidis@sunlight.gr
10	Paspalas	Konstantinos	SUNLIGHT	k.paspalas@sunlight.gr
11	Tsalakis	Apostolos	CERTH	tsolakis@iti.gr
12	Zikos	Stylios	CERTH	szikos@iti.gr

REVIEWERS LIST

List of Reviewers (in alphabetic order)				
#	Surname	First Name	Beneficiary	Contact email
1	Canuti	Federico	GLASSUP	federico.canuti@glassup.net
2	Daniele	Radogna	REGOLA	d.radogna@regola.it

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LIST OF DEFINITIONS & ABBREVIATIONS

Abbreviation	Explanation or definition
2D	Two-dimensional
3D	Three-dimensional
API	Application programming interface
AR	Augmented reality
BSC	Business Scenario
CAD	Computer aided design
CRUD	In computer programming, create, read, update and delete are the four basic functions of persistent storage
DCC	Digital Content Creation
DFD	Data flow diagram, a diagramming methodology to specify processes
DG RTD	European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation
DMAIC	Acronym for Define, Measure, Analyse, Improve and Control. Refers to a data-driven improvement cycle used for improving, optimizing and stabilizing business processes and designs.
DOW	The Description of Work, a formal SatisFactory project document
EC	European Commission
ECOGRAI	A method to design and to implement Performance Indicator Systems (PIS) for industrial organizations.
EFQM	European Foundation for Quality Management
EOP	Emergency Operating Procedures
EU	European Union
H2020	Horizon 2020 is the biggest EU Research and Innovation programme ever, with nearly €80 billion of funding available over 7 years (2014 to 2020)
HMD	Head Mounted Display
ICT	Information and communication technology
KPI	Key performance Indicator

HMI	Human Machine Interface
JDK	Java Development Kit
LMS	Learning Management Systems
M20	SatisFactory project Milestone at Month 20
M30	SatisFactory project Milestone at Month 30
MOOC	Massive Open Online Courses
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport is a lightweight messaging protocol for small sensors and mobile devices, optimized for high-latency or unreliable networks
OM	Ontology Manager
OP	Operating Procedures
PIS	Performance Indicator System
RGBD	Red, Green, Blue, Depth. Imaging technology providing multi spectral images where the three optical bands: R, G, B, are coupled with a distance (time of flight) reading
SCM	Supply chain management
SDK	Software Development Kit
SLIC	Simple Linear Iterative Clustering
SOP	Standard Operating Procedures
TCT	Training Creation tool
TEP	Training and educational platform
TPM	Total Productive Maintenance
TPT	Training Presentation tool
TS	Training system
TM	Talent management
UC	Use Case
U.N.	United Nations
VR	Virtual reality

1. EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This document is a deliverable of the SatisFactory project, funded by the European Commission's Directorate-General for Research and Innovation (DG RTD), under its Horizon 2020 Research and innovation programme (H2020). It describes the intended achievement of T6.6, i.e. the End-users VR-enabled training material and scenarios. The work covered by this deliverable includes the tools and procedures to use in the training sessions of T6.3.3 as well as the raw material gathered for each tool and use case and methodology to convert this material into step-by-step training procedures. Furthermore, the selection of "VR-capable" use cases is explained based on the applicability of 3D representation of specific actions by the end users.

In this document, in Section 2, after the introduction into the purpose and scope of this deliverable, the user requirements are summarized based on the work conducted in T1.1 as well as in T4.3.

This is followed in Section 3, by the definition of User groups involved in training and education of workers on the job as these were defined in detail in T1.2, as well as their roles and different aspects of training they require. The use cases governing the general aspects of training as they have already been defined in T1.2 are summarized and put into context with regard to training on the use of the end-user oriented tools of SatisFactory. The tools that are selected from among the complete toolset of SatisFactory to be covered by the training sessions and respective material and scenarios are then described in short. Finally, an overview of the methodology behind the development of the training material and scenarios is provided based on the concepts of on-the-job training using multimedia material and the use of VR elements.

In Section 4, a short description of the Training Platform used in the development and deployment of the material developed is made, as well as a critical selection of the scenarios that involve VR elements based on the applicability of 3D content to them. The VR-Enabled Training Platform is none other than the AROP Training Platform developed in T4.3 applied to the scenarios that cover the use of the SatisFactory tools.

In Section 5, for each of the tools covered by the training sessions, the basic functionalities and elements are presented similar in form to that of a user manual explain what are the uses of each tool, who is it used by, and where and how are all the functionalities accessed from either within a computer application interface or in the case of some of the end-user oriented tools the tangible objects and devices used.

This work of gathering all of the required material for the training sessions culminates in Section 6 where the step-by-step training scenarios for each of the tools covered in this deliverable are presented. The material used in the scenarios covers textual descriptions as well as screenshots, video, 3D animations and other material gathered. As such, all the material gathered in conventional form (text, images, video etc) as well as 3D animations (where applicable) have been combined to develop the training procedures in the format used by the AROP Training Platform.

In the conclusions, the final development of the training material is recapped along with the challenges faced and the overview on how the work carried out in this task will support the training sessions planned within T6.3.3.

2. INTRODUCTION

2.1 PURPOSE, CONTEXT AND SCOPE OF THIS DELIVERABLE

As stressed in the executive summary, the aim behind the development of the VR-enabled training material and scenarios is to promote the use of the SatisFactory tools within real-world applications. As such, the initial work carried out within the scope of this task was to identify the needs of the workers and the use cases where the use of the SatisFactory tools would have the greatest impact with regard to end-user participation and quick uptake of the concepts and functionalities of the tools. Therefore, the main purpose of this deliverable is the development of novel FoF compliant training material to train factory personnel in the use of novel FoF tools and services.

Right from the start, it became evident that in order to promote the SatisFactory toolset it was imperative that the same tools and methodologies developed within the project with regard to training on the shopfloor should be used to facilitate the training of users on the use of the SatisFactory tools themselves. This realization was the driving force behind the methodology used to determine the tools to be covered by the training scenarios, the types of material to be used for each tool that better conveys the correct way to use them, the generation of this material and the organization of the material into step-by-step training scenarios.

The scope of the material gathered during the work carried out within this task covers 11 tools in total and involved carefully writing instructions of use for each tool, covering the most important use cases that employ them, then acquiring photographs, screenshots and diagrams visually accentuating the written instructions as well as capturing entire sequences that correspond to use scenarios in video or screencasts. This material was then split up into 31 scenarios to each of which the relevant audiovisual material was attributed to. Furthermore, the video sequences depicting these scenarios were cut into segments demonstrating each step involved in each scenario. Using this audiovisual material as templates, where applicable, 3D models of objects, tools and equipment used in the use case were created and animated to convey their proper use.

The raw material gathered along with the edited audiovisual content and the generated 3D animated content were then meticulously combined into AROP Procedures using the AROP Training Platform Creation tool. This involved the generation of the procedure tree, the assignment of Descriptive Layers to each Action in the procedure, exporting of the procedure as a bundle to be downloaded and used in the AROP Presentation Tool which will be followed in the next period with the deployment of these training procedure bundles to the Training procedure web servers installed at the pilot sites of COMAU, Sunlight and CPERI.

2.2 REQUIREMENTS

The specific requirements driving the design and implementation of the training material and scenarios that will be used to acquaint end users with the SatisFactory solutions, are a subset of the more general requirements listed in the deliverable D1.1.1 titled: "User group definitions, end-user needs, requirement analysis and development guidelines". It is a document that is a formal

deliverable of the T1.1 task of the SatisFactory project. In the following table we include a selection of the requirements that are strictly related to the AR Training platform and, for this reason, have been not mentioned in the D4.3.1. Please, refer to the D4.3.1 for a list of the requirements related to the A.R. in-Factory platform; further, refer to D1.1.1 for the whole requirement set and for an explanation of the widely known methodologies adopted for their definition.

Key	Summary	Priority	Description	Fit Criterion
SAFA-52	Multimedia training procedures	Blocker	Video or audio recorded procedures could be available for new operators and technicians	There are several training procedures can be performed through multimedia platform
SAFA-47	Platform training	Minor	The introduction of new terminals could lead to the introduction of new training in order to let the people work with these new devices	A manual to use the platform is available
SAFA-37	Multimedia training procedures	Blocker	IT architecture provides an innovative training environment that allows multimedia training procedures and sessions	At least 1 training procedure can be performed through multimedia platform

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3. TRAINING PROCEDURES METHODOLOGY

3.1 SPECIFIC USER NEEDS: THE CURRENT ISSUES

The main issues in the training activities currently carried out are related to the huge amount of specific, additional paperwork required by them. Further, there is a significant need for additional resources “needed to train the trainees” on the use of the SatisFactory tools. The adoption of the innovative training platform developed by the SatisFactory project as part of T4.3 is going to address these issues in full, providing a Training Platform always available and always up-to-date, media-rich bundle. Moreover, the training Presentation tool can provide VR representations of some of the activities performed by the users while working with SatisFactory components.

3.2 USERS / ACTORS: CASE SCENARIOS

In scenarios involving training on the use of SatisFactory tools is expected to be applied to two different categories of workers:

1. The “blue collars”, i.e. the operators that physically need training. Reasons for the training could be the following:
 - 1.1. They are workers regardless of their experience on the operations involved in their line of work, they have never used the solutions provided by SatisFactory. These persons need to learn the procedures required to operate the SatisFactory tools. As with Standard Operating Procedures, this training without the use of the training facilities provided by SatisFactory is usually performed placing the new workers side by side with experienced operators that transfer to them their knowledge with training on the job, as well as providing documents that describe step by step the operations.
 - 1.2. Some updates are required in the existing procedures in order to accommodate the introduction of SatisFactory tools in the SOPs. Workers already in the company may require training because of procedures change or updates required. Typically, these updates are communicated to operators giving them printed procedures to be followed step by step and cycle after cycle, until they are learned and the print is not needed anymore.
2. The Technical Leaders, as well as the Supervisors, Administrators and Managers, that are in charge of the shopfloor management and administration as well as worker support during training and operation. They as well are not accustomed to the use of the toolset provided by SatisFactory but are mostly involved in the operation of ICT tools, whereas the blue collars may also operate tangible tools and equipment on-the-job.

In both cases, the users targeted by the training procedures and material produced in this deliverable are expected to be able to integrate the SatisFactory tools in their day-to-day operations based on the training sessions they will follow using this material within the scope of T6.3.3.

3.2.1 User Groups Targeted for Training on SatisFactory Components

The Training and Education platform mostly aims at novice and/or trainee workers in order to show to them various procedures to be performed in the shop floor using the SatisFactory toolset. Furthermore, even experienced workers can be assisted by means of the platform when a difficult or a completely new procedure must currently be carried out in the shop floor. The following list shows, for each shop floor, the groups of workers who can be involved in the training operations and that will possibly benefit from the training (or the on the job training) at the three shopfloors involved in the project.

COMAU:

COMAU's actors that are involved at SatisFactory project belong to three categories (Technical Leader, Process operator, Design and Ergonomic engineer). This categorization is based on their role and on the procedures that they usually perform. Two of these categories can greatly benefit from the educational and training activities. More specifically:

- **Process operator.** According to the task to be carried out, specialized operations have to be performed by skilled operators.
- **Design and ergonomic engineer.** They are involved mainly with: the design of layout of machines; the mechanical design; the electrical/software/hydraulic design; the ergonomics and safety issues.

The third group is the Technical Leader that could use ad hoc training sessions when he or she starts working at the specific environment as a trainee or novice.

SUNLIGHT:

In both lines that are involved in the SATISFACTORY project, staff with different responsibilities are involved. They are grouped into the following categories:

1. Plant manager;
2. Production planner;
3. Production supervisors;
4. Shop floor leaders and workers (expert, novice).

Also a technical and maintenance team (technicians, technical manager) is kept in standby to react, should unplanned incidents occur. The categories that can benefit from the educational and training activities are:

1. **Technicians.** They are responsible for handling the training and the development needs of new hires and for implementing preventive maintenance programs.
2. **Foreman.** Coordinates daily production floor activities and delegate assignments to production personnel monitoring employee's work performances relative to expectations and maintaining material/workflow through the facility
3. **Workers.** Involved with measuring, grading and feeding batches of raw materials into production machinery. They operate production line equipment and assemble goods in a production line.

The other groups (Maintenance Manager, Production supervisor and Production Plant manager) could use ad hoc training sessions when a specific need arises.

CERTH/CPERI:

At CERTH/CPERI shop floor there are two main categories of actors; one related to the process operations and the other to the maintenance activities, whereas both are coordinated and supervised by the “Floor Manager”. Also the maintenance team is broken into three categories of groups according to the area of expertise, namely the mechanical-process, the electrical, and the automation related group. The categories that can benefit from the educational and training activities are:

1. **Process technician.** Supports and maintains pilot plants operation and is involved in new constructions and revamps.
2. **Electrical technician.** Responsible for maintaining schematics, electrical cabinets, is involved in new constructions and revamps.
3. **Automation technician.** Responsible for maintaining automation and ICT infrastructures and is involved in new constructions and revamps.
4. **Process operator.** Performs Daily operations at the pilot plants.

The groups that have been identified as candidate to use the On the Job Training and Educational Platform can benefit not only of the new training procedures, when they are available, but also of the help received in remembering procedures that they have not performed for a significant period of time. More details about the characteristics and aspects of the actors can be found at deliverable “D1.2 - Use Case Analysis and Application Scenarios Description”.

3.2.2 Use Cases Covered in Training

The category of SatisFactory UC-2 “Learning environment with interactive training activities for multi-purpose operations” deals with the learning environment involved in interactive training activities for the multi-purpose operations that are performed at each shop floor. This category includes the following three UCs:

1. UC-2.1: In-factory training and support of workers using a flexible learning platform

This UC drafts the use of the dynamically expanding and semantically enhanced knowledge base together with the Collaboration tools using the communication platform. It will activate the training activities to be used by the Multi Modal and Augmented HMI and the SSN components, which are involved in training (AR Glasses and Other A.R. devices). This UC is executed by the involved actors without the need of the sustained attention of an educator.

2. UC-2.3: Presentation of the shop floor procedures utilizing heterogeneous material

The main objective of this UC is to provide the necessary steps of the actions required by the procedures and to be performed by the involved workers in order to use at the best the information and the knowledge derived by the SCM and the Repository. The Operational Platform will be used in order to make available the necessary steps for the aggregation of the requested procedures upon request. The shop floor workers and technicians will have a detailed description using sources such as schematics, multiple-media content, manuals or standard operating procedures in combination with the historical information for each situation or event that they will be involved with.

The above UCs mostly use the Training and Education platform to support workers at the shop floors. The goal is to provide the necessary information to the workers in order to be able to perform some of their tasks better, quicker and safer. Furthermore, there are other UCs that interact with the main UCs of the Training and Educational platform. These UCs are:

1. UC-1.1: Process for handling shop floor related information.
2. UC-6.2: Provide optimum actions and instructions with customized dynamic information.
3. UC-6.3: Knowledge sharing among workers based on advanced reasoning.

These UCs provide the appropriate functions and information to UC2 and facilitate the seamless data exchange with the existing systems or the intuitive interaction with the involved workers.

Various components have been developed and are utilized in the SatisFactory ecosystem in order to support the different functionalities required for making industrial environments more attractive to workers. The components that have been developed can be classified into the following categories, based on their functionality.

SatisFactory component categories	Indicative example
Sensors/Devices	Comfort sensors AR Glasses device
Components providing semantically enriched information	Localization Manager Semantic framework
Components for decision support	iDSS
Incident detection components	Incident detection engine using Depth / IR cameras
Components facilitating integration of systems	LinksSmart middleware AR Glasses Device Manager
Component for data storage	SatisFactory repository
Components for supporting training activities	On-the-job training tool

Components for collaboration enhancement	Social Collaboration Platform, Gamification Platform
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Table 1: Categories of SatisFactory components

It is worth noting that some of these components are considered back-end components and are not used directly by the end users. However, they are vital for the proper operation of the system as a whole, as they provide the services and the mechanisms required by higher-level end user components. Some of the main SatisFactory back-end components are listed for reference below:

- Sensors part of smart sensor network
- Repository (CIDEM)
- LinksSmart middleware
- Semantic Context manager
- Incident detection engine
- AR In-Factory Platform (back-end)
- HR scheduling engine

The SatisFactory components that involve end users are presented in the following section. As the personnel of the shop floor directly interacts with these components on a daily basis, the creation of training activities and guidelines regarding the use of the particular components is important, in order to fully exploit the new functionalities that are introduced on the shop floor by these modules.

3.3 SATISFACTORY COMPONENTS COVERED

Training material or activities have been created for the end users of the following SatisFactory components. These specific components were selected as they either (a) provide information to the end users or (b) have to be administered or controlled by the end users. Some of these components, such as the on-the-job training tools and the AR Glasses are used directly by the workers, other components such as the iDSS and the HR Workload Balancing Toolkit are used by supervisors or managers, while some components such as the gamification platform and the suggestion platform involve all personnel trades.

3.3.1 On-the-Job Training Creation Tool

The On-the-Job Training Creation Tool gives the possibility to create training procedures either from scratch or from an existing operating procedure.

The trainer can define training sessions simply by selecting, from the library of the training procedures, the most suitable ones to define the goal of the session under editing. This approach gives high flexibility to the training session concept, because a training procedure can be reused in multiple sessions, if it is useful for the purpose. According to this scenario, the library of the training procedures is composed by single, elementary, specific training tasks that could be arranged by the trainer in a more complex procedure finely tuned to fit the training needs of a specific individual.

3.3.2 On-the-Job Training Presentation Tool

The On-the-Job Training Presentation Tool is a Unity application able to navigate the bundle that is the output of the Creation Tools. It has the capability of navigating the procedure step by step, following sequences, loops, conditions included in the procedure and, in doing this, it delivers the content which has been previously managed and included as resource by the Creation Tool. It can communicate with the other SatisFactory components mainly via LinkSmart middleware.

The On-the-Job Training Presentation Tool provides a rich set of visualization and interaction functionalities in order to present previously prepared A.R. SOP directly “on the job”. By using this tool, operators can follow a specific procedure step by step and obtain support for their current task. Furthermore, the operators have the opportunity to choose the best content that fits their own needs among the contents that can be deployed and delivered in the platform they are actually using. Lastly, the On-the-job Training Presentation Tool has integrated the gesture recognition system for implementing an alternative human machine interface for application navigation.

3.3.3 Shopfloor Management Platform

The Shopfloor Management Platform is comprised of the following components.

3.3.3.1 iDSS

The main objectives of the integrated Decision Support System (iDSS) component are to increase productivity, reduce downtime, improve safety and streamline incident management. The iDSS receives real-time data coming from the shop floor through a “plug-and-share” multi-sensor monitoring framework. It is also able to dispatch information to different devices, such as Augmented Reality devices, in order to notify the workers about important events. iDSS also provides a variety of visual tools and graphic interfaces to meet the current needs of a factory. The DSS Core is the core component of iDSS and is the place that all the automatic procedures and calculations takes place. The DSS Core is equipped with a powerful rule engine that aids the intelligence of the various components of the iDSS.

The Visual and Real-time analytics is another component of the iDSS, which supports the simultaneous analysis of many pairs of time series. This particular component also gives a general overview of the status of a factory in real-time, by monitoring the status of each element that is attached to it. The end user can select between two operating modes: the online and the offline mode. In the online mode, real-time data are requested and processed, while in the offline mode, historical data are loaded given the desired time interval.

3.3.3.2 HR Workload Management Toolkit

The Human Resources (HR) Workload Management toolkit increases performance and productivity in dynamically changing environments by optimizing HR workload balancing and task assignment. The toolkit is comprised of the Work Schedule Management Toolkit and the Visualization Toolkit.

The Work Schedule Management Toolkit automatically produces the initial schedule according to selected preferences and constraints. It also provides automated task prioritization and HR suitability

ranking, together with customized notifications to employees based on the business needs. The dynamic HR scheduling engine is able to schedule new tasks in real-time and re-adapt the work schedule automatically when necessary. Furthermore, it can re-adapt the assignment of tasks to employees towards improving workload balancing.

The Visualization Toolkit allows managers to supervise the shop floor at a glance, in a single and highly customizable view. Three views are currently available in the Visualization Toolkit, namely the map view, the work-schedule view and the incident replay view. The first view is in charge of showing the shop floor with both the machinery and the workers. The second view allows to dynamically analyzing the current work-schedule highlighting the interactions between the different actors. Lastly, the third view allows to quickly watch and re-play past video recordings of events happened in the factory.

3.3.3.3 Maintenance toolkit

Note: The Maintenance Toolkit is a subcomponent of iDSS.

The Maintenance toolkit is a tool for registering maintenance procedures, keeping maintenance records, managing information and schematics of physical assets. The Maintenance Toolkit is a key-part of iDSS, as it provides the necessary context to iDSS. It supports the B2MML standard and provides models and static data to SatisFactory system. The Maintenance Toolkit is a web application built on top of an existing CMMS system (AIMMS). It is responsible for receiving triggers of malfunction from the Incident Detection toolkit and distributing messages about maintenance tasks to all the other SatisFactory components through CIDEM and LinkSmart. Maintenance Toolkit's main functionality is the creation of maintenance tasks on the shop floor, as it is fully equipped with information about the workers, assets and spare parts necessary to perform a maintenance task.

The supervisor can create a new task using the toolkit's 'New Task' tab. From there, several attributes about the task are defined, such as the asset, the category and the description of the task, the initiator of the task, the worker's trade responsible for the task, the criticality of the task, and the name of the responsible worker. The Maintenance Toolkit is able to create a calendar in which the daily tasks are shown. The calendar can be daily, weekly, or monthly, and contains information such as the responsible workers for the tasks, the estimated duration of the task etc. A shop floor manager can change the order of the tasks based on their preferences or the knowledge of the operations on the shop floor. Furthermore, the Maintenance Toolkit allows the supervisor to manage the assets. The supervisor configures the details and schematics concerning each asset, and then the Maintenance Toolkit provides this information to CIDEM repository using the B2MML format.

3.3.4 Shopfloor Feedback Engine

Note: The Shopfloor Feedback Engine is a sub-component of iDSS.

The Shopfloor Feedback Engine is a mobile application for the worker that provides a handful way so that he/she can be notified about various alerts and receive information about their daily work schedule, malfunctions that occur in the assets, and unexpected changes in production. Furthermore, it enables the worker to give feedback concerning the process followed to complete

the task assigned to him/her, the task duration, the status of the maintenance process etc. The Shopfloor Feedback Engine is integrated with the Maintenance Toolkit and DSS Core and it can provide detailed instructions of the maintenance, schematics of assets, and other information to the worker. Additionally, the engine supports bidirectional communication with other components and toolkits. For example, when a worker detects an incident in the shop floor, he can use the Shop Floor Feedback Engine to send back a message. The message can be either sent to the Maintenance Toolkit or the DSS Core for decision and prediction. The main idea behind the Shop Floor Feedback Engine is to facilitate workers and provide them with a toolkit that is portable and easy to access throughout the whole shop floor.

The worker enters his/her credentials in the initial login screen. After a successful authentication, the worker can view his/her tasks or all the available tasks in the 'Tasks' screen. Detailed information about a task is shown in the 'Details' screen. When a task is chosen in the Shop Floor Feedback Engine application, more information is shown to the user: the responsible technicians, the instructions that should be followed and attachments with useful documents and pictures (schemas, malfunction photos). The worker can change the status of the task by pressing the appropriate button. In particular, a task can be declared as in progress by pressing the 'Start' button or can be declared as completed by pressing the 'End' button.

3.3.5 Visual Training Data Analytics Tool (TDAT)

The Training Data Analytics tool is the application intended to provide valuable insight into the training sessions. This is achieved by transforming the log data provided by the Presentation tool into working in firmly established Key Performance Indicators (KPIs). These KPIs are then visualized in a way that is suitable to get a better understanding of the overall process to be used to improve the training operating procedures. The KPIs are further processed to provide higher level of knowledge by means of the Ontology Manager (OM).

The visualization tool for Training Data Analytics enables the operators to review and understand both raw KPI, produced by the Training Data Analytics tool, and the KPI produced by the semantic rules coded by means of the Ontology Manager.

3.3.6 Localization Manager

The SatisFactory Localization Manager uses Ultra Wide Band (UWB) wearable devices to provide real-time production monitoring and ensure a safer work environment. The wearable device can be attached to any piece of equipment or clothing. The Localization Manager provides punctual information about positioning of personnel within the shop floor. The positions of personnel are displayed in a Map View in a gbXML contextualized and mapped environment, providing a comprehensive abstraction of the shop floor level to the supervisors. The Localization Manager component can also provide geo-fencing events when a worker approaches a restricted area. Furthermore, the component can offer insights to correct workers' postures and shop floor ergonomics, by taking into account the data from the inertial sensor in the wearable device for estimating the orientation of the worker.

3.3.7 AR Glasses

The goal of the AR Glasses in the SatisFactory project is to increase the attractiveness of the working environment in the shop floor and, at the same time, to provide each worker with an easy-to-use and effective tool that could help the worker in the daily tasks. The Augmented Reality (AR) Glasses device that has been developed is WiFi enabled and integrates a REST API for sending/receiving data.

A worker equipped with the AR Glasses is able to receive important notifications in a convenient way without the need for interrupting the ongoing work. A notification can be presented as a text message, an image or an audio message that is played on the connected earphones. A notification can be an alert that has triggered by the incident detection engine, for example when a worker enters into an area in the shop floor that has been marked as forbidden. Moreover, the use of the AR Glasses allows a worker to perform on-the-job training by presenting images and text on the display, for each step of a procedure. A worker is also able to receive remote assistance on request, through the social collaboration platform. Information, such as instructions and diagrams, which is provided by the supervisor is shown on the AR Glasses display. Furthermore, the supervisor can remotely evaluate the situation by viewing the video stream of the AR Glasses' camera.

3.3.8 Suggestions Platform

The Suggestions Platform is a web-based tool, where suggestions for improvement can be entered by the personnel. The user interface of the Suggestions Platform is optimized with regard to usability so that suggestions can be entered quickly. The platform is used by workers, supervisors or managers. In the case a worker has an idea how to overcome a problem in the daily work process, he/she can connect to the Suggestions Platform from a mobile device and fill out the few mandatory forms in order to add the new suggestion. A supervisor or manager can respond to a suggestion, by connecting to the Suggestions Platform from his/her office computer. A suggestion can be approved, approved with modifications or be rejected. In the latter case, the supervisor has to enter the reason for rejection. The response to a suggestion is fed back to the worker who entered the suggestion.

3.3.9 Digital Andon / Gesture Control Management

The objective of the Gesture and Content Recognition Manager (GCRM) is the processing of video streams received by video cameras (Microsoft Kinect 2). The output of the processing is a large set of services which can be exploited by other SatisFactory modules. The Gesture and Content Recognition Manager offers vision-based cutting-edge technologies at shop floor level by preserving the privacy of the workers.

The Gesture and Content Recognition Manager supports presence detection in the Smart Assembly Station. Furthermore, it is able to recognize workers' movements (e.g. specific gestures, falls, etc.) and triggers respective actions in real-time, allowing human-machine interaction without physical touch. Another interesting functionality that GCRM offers is the detection of specific safety equipment, which allows to identify whether workers wear the necessary equipment (e.g. jacket), contributing to automating safety monitoring.

The Digital Andon is a SatisFactory component that represents a Novel HMI and is deployed at the shop floor level. It acts as a content management system and allows multilayer data visualization. This component adds the advance functionality of display dynamic information, creating multiple layers. Each layer is provided with its own regions and resources in order to increase the dynamic nature of the component itself, allowing third-party in-factory components to draw on every SatisFactory enabled display in a more comprehensive manner, by addressing directly the desired resource through the exposed API. All Digital Andon functionalities are accessible using a REST API.

The Digital Andon for smart assembly station (Digital Andon St) guarantees a seamless integration between a user and a machine. The former simply moves his body and the latter reacts accordingly. The hands-free interaction is guaranteed via the GCRM gesture recognition, which is in charge of decoding the meaning of the gestures performed by the users and sends the correspondent signals to the Digital Andon St. The Digital Andon St supports the inclusion of images, pdf files, and videos as content.

3.3.10 Social Collaboration Platform

The goal of the Social Collaboration Platform of SatisFactory is to increase the workers' autonomy and facilitate knowledge transfer through the support of interpersonal communication, problem solving and continuous learning. The Social Collaboration Platform is a web application that follows the server-client architectural approach. It allows the real-time communication among the users via text messages (chat messenger). Groups of users can also be created, making collaboration among members belonging to the same team easier. Furthermore, the end users can share files and have easy access to multimedia content. The platform includes a search tool for activities, videos and users. It also provides advanced functionalities to the end users, such as remote assistance by integrating communication with the AR Glasses. Lastly, the Social Collaboration Platform provides also a dashboard to the end user, which presents statistical data that are produced after processing historical information, in a concise manner, using advanced visualization tools.

3.3.11 Gamification Platform

The SatisFactory Gamification Platform is a web-based component which allows the personnel to participate in gamified activities. Gamifying activities that are not performed often or well enough, has the potential to motivate workers to perform these activities more efficiently and raise their popularity. The overall gamification approach shall add a fun aspect to work and help in increasing the overall attractiveness of the workplace. An external component can communicate with the Gamification Platform via REST calls.

The Gamification Platform allows the manager who has administrator rights to create a game by entering a description of a game and its settings. Each game belongs to a category and can be either for teams or for individuals. When creating a game, the user defines the actions, the awards and the rules (different types are supported). Users who participate in a game have access to various information regarding the game, as they are able to view who is participating in the game and view

the leaderboard of the game. Moreover, the gained awards for each user can be shown, as well as all games that a user participates in and the points the user has gained.

3.4 TRAINING MATERIAL AND SCENARIO AUTHORIZING METHODOLOGY

Based on the work conducted in T4.3, the training methodology that has been developed consists of the following steps:

- Selection of tools/components
- Creation of a user guide for each tool
- Definition of the main use case scenarios for each tool
- Acquisition of audiovisual material
- Editing of the audio visual material for each step in each scenario
- Creation of 3D models objects, tools and equipment
- Use of the AROP Training Platform Creation Tool to create AROP Procedures for each scenario
- Exporting of the procedures to be used by the AROP Presentation Tool
- Deployment to the pilot sites

Selection of tools

In this initial step, the SatisFactory tools that are used by the end users were identified. As it has been previously mentioned, various SatisFactory tools are back-end tools which do not require any special interaction with the end users. Therefore, these tools were excluded from the training scenarios. As described in section 3.3, 11 tools were finally selected to be included in the training scenarios. For these tools, the system supports end users' training activities through utilization of training material.

Creation of a user guide for each tool

A user guide contains the instructions of use for a particular tool. This is an important step, as all the functionalities of the tool are described in an officially written format. As the interaction of the tool with the end users is of high interest in the training scenarios, the requirements of the tool regarding its interaction with the end users are also documented. Apart from the detailed reference of all functionalities, a user guide usually contains a section which refers to the installation of the tool and a section which describes the most important functionalities in a concise manner (quick guide) for easy reference.

Definition of the main use case scenarios for each tool

Through the analysis of the instructions that were written in the previous step when creating the user guides, the main use case scenarios are extracted for each tool. The most demanding and complex procedures and functionalities of each tool are included in the training use case scenarios and must be well-documented.

Acquisition of audiovisual material

Based on the written instructions included in the user guide of a tool and the main use case scenarios that were defined in the previous step, the corresponding audiovisual material is acquired. This is raw material that is going to be utilized in the training sessions after being processed at a later stage.

The audiovisual material can be in various formats depending on the tool and its use case scenarios. For example, it can include photographs, screenshots and diagrams. Furthermore, videos or screencasts are also used for capturing entire sequences of activities, depending on the use case scenarios.

Editing of the audiovisual material for each step in each scenario

Audiovisual material is edited at this step, in order to be better organized. More specifically, video sequences depicting scenarios as a whole, were cut into segments. Each video segment refers to each particular step involved in the corresponding scenario.

Creation of 3D models objects, tools and equipment

In this step, 3D models of objects, tools and equipment were created using the audiovisual material already collected, where applicable. The audiovisual material is used as templates for the creation of 3D models. The use of 3D models in training scenarios is helpful because it enhances the user's experience and interaction. Furthermore, based on the 3D models created, 3D animations of the models were then rendered in order to show the proper use of the objects and the equipment.

Use of the AROP Training Platform Creation Tool to create AROP Procedures for each scenario

After processing the audiovisual material and the creation of the 3D models required, the AROP Training Platform Creation Tool is utilized in order to create the AROP Procedures for each scenario. The Creation Tool allows the definition of a procedure in terms of operations, phases and actions. A procedure is defined as a tree, enabling its execution according to a well-defined navigation model. Each element in a procedure can be refined. For each action, the level of detail (Descriptive Layer) can be set. The Descriptive Layer provides several content types for describing how an action has to be performed, such as plain text, images, videos, audio clips, 3D models and documents.

Exporting of the procedures to be used by the AROP Presentation Tool

After creating a procedure for a specific scenario using the AROP Training Platform Creation Tool, the Package to Bundle Tool is utilized. The Package to Bundle Tool transforms the procedure, as internally represented as project by the AROP Training Platform Creation Tool, into a bundle that can be opened and parsed by the AROP Presentation Tool. To this end, the Package to Bundle tool collects all the resources found in the procedure and performs all the possible transformations and optimizations applicable for the destination platform where the Presentation Tool is going to be run. It is worth noting that the Package to Bundle tool is used directly by the AROP Training Platform Creation Tool and is transparent to the end user.

Deployment to the pilot sites

For the deployment of the training procedure bundles, created at the previous step, to the pilot sites (COMAU, Sunlight, CPERI), a Training procedure web server has to be setup in each site. The AROP Presentation Tool makes the appropriate requests to the Training procedure web server in order to acquire the training procedure bundles required in a specific scenario. As the Training procedure web server may contain sensitive information of the company/organization, all the recommended practices have to be considered in order to ensure security. For instance, the web server can be accessible only via the local network.

4. VR-ENABLED TRAINING PLATFORM

The AR Training platform designed and developed in the task T4.3 is the fundamental tool used in the generation and deployment of the training material on the end-user use of Satisfactory components. When researching and debating the selection/development of a specific tool for the deployment of VR-capable training material, it became evident that the toolset created in T2.5/T4.3 was more than capable and applicable to use in the scope of the requirements of T6.5 since the same training methodology and requirements used in SOPs is also applicable in training end-users on the use of Satisfactory components.

The methodology presented in Section 3.4 is the basis upon which the AR Training Platform was used to develop the training scenarios. The training platform consists of two tools:

- The AROP Training Creation tool and
- The AROP Training Presentation Tool

4.1 THE AROP CREATION TOOL

The Creation Tool of the AR Training Platform is a versatile training procedure authoring program that as presented in Section 5.1.1 is capable of defining complex operations and combining several different types of audiovisual material to create a multimedia presentation of the training procedure as a step-by-step tutorial.

Figure 1 The AROP Creation Tool used to author the Gesture Control Management training scenario

The work involved into authoring the training scenarios, involves first defining the steps required to fulfil an operation as this is the outline of how each step will be associated with the material to be

added into the procedure. This is the work carried out in Section 6, and the result of that work for each one of the 31 training scenarios defined for the use of the 11 tools covered by the training material is translated into a procedure tree similar to the one presented in Figure 1.

Figure 2 Video screencast of the “Swipe right to move to previous instruction” Action

Figure 3 3D Animation of the “Swipe right to move to previous instruction” Action

As explained both in Section 5.1.1 and in step-by-step instructions in 6.1.1.1, the Creation tool is capable of incorporating various types of descriptive layers for each Action carried out within a training procedure. This means that within the training material gathered for each tool, there are textual descriptions, images, diagrams, screenshots and photos as well as video captures and screencasts to enhance the visual elements describing each action. This audiovisual material was edited and especially when video was concerned was cut into segments representing each step

defined in the training scenario and then added to the training procedure. An example of this is presented in Figure 2. Furthermore, for those scenarios where VR representations are applicable (these are covered in the next section), 3D animations were also included in the procedure (Figure 3).

4.2 THE AROP PRESENTATION TOOL

The tool used to present the training procedure to the trainees is the AROP Presentation tool. This tool as explained in 5.1.2 is capable of presenting a procedure as a step-by-step process on an Android tablet device or a PC as well as on the GlassUp AR glasses using several descriptive layers on top of each action described in text and also provide the ability to view VR representations as well as AR representations of activities with the use of image targets, or with markerless object recognition. In the scope of the training material produced for the sessions involving the training on the Satisfactory tools themselves, the use of AR is not applicable or necessary.

The step-by-step instructions on how to use the tool are described in Section 6.1.2.1. It is very straightforward and can be deployed on the shopfloor without the need of an instructor present.

Figure 4 A typical training procedure as viewed in the AROP Presentation Tool

Figure 5 A typical VR-enabled presentation of an action in the AROP Presentation Tool

4.3 APPLICABILITY OF VIRTUAL REALITY (VR) ON TRAINING SCENARIOS

Most of the tools of Satisfactory that are oriented towards end-users involve the use of ICT programs executed either on a PC or a mobile device such as a tablet or mobile phone which makes them not suitable for representation in VR mode (in 3D animation form). However, there are a few cases where 3D animations can better represent some activities as for example the scenario presented in the previous section regarding 3D animated demonstration of the Gesture Control System. These cases mostly apply to the tools where tangible objects and equipment other than normal computing devices are used. As indicated in section 3.3 the tools covered with training scenarios are the following:

Tool	Scenarios	Tool type
On-the-Job Training Creation Tool	1	Computer Application
On-the-Job Training Presentation Tool	1	Mobile Application
Shopfloor Management Platform	5	Computer Application
Shopfloor Feedback Android Tool	1	Mobile Application
Visual Training Data Analytics Tool (TDAT)	3	Computer Application
Localization Manager	1	Wearable + Application
AR Glasses	4	Wearable + Application
Suggestions Platform	4	Computer Application
Digital Andon / Gesture Control Management	2	Natural interaction
Social Collaboration Platform	7	Computer Application
Gamification Platform	1	Computer Application

Of the 11 tools above, 8 are explicitly ICT applications executed either on a PC or a mobile device. This indicated that any tutorial on their use has no benefit of 3D representations since all the steps involved in the training scenarios involve the use of a 2D screen and an input device that is either a mouse+keyboard or a touch interface on the 2D screen of a tablet.

The 3 tools that are better candidates for the use of VR representations are the following:

- **Localization Manager**
The localization manager involves the use of a wearable transceiver and is applied on a large scale of area where the wearer can move freely, while on the other end a supervisor is using a computer to track the motion and location of the wearer. The training scenario covers both the movement in actual space as well as the tracking of that motion on a top down view of that area on a computer. Here, a 3D animation representing what happens when a worker enters a restricted area is an apt case where a VR representation can be used.
- **AR Glasses**
The GlassUp AR Glasses are a tangible device worn by the worker accompanied by a basic input device with the ability to use the Gesture Control system in order to provide interaction with the running application on the glasses. As such, a 3D representation on how to use the glasses is applicable in this case.
- **Digital Andon / Gesture Control Management**
Similarly to the AR Glasses, the Digital Andon is a device that a worker can interact with using gestures instead of a typical interaction device such as a mouse, keyboard or touch input. As such scenarios involving 3D animations of the sequences of motions required for the correct use of the Digital Andon are applicable here as well

5. TRAINING MATERIAL

5.1 CORE USER FUNCTIONALITIES

5.1.1 AR On-the-Job Training Creation Tool

5.1.1.1 Purpose and features

The AR OP Creation Tool allows you to design interactive procedures using:

- Resources
- Operations
- Steps
- Actions
- Relations

Using the AR OP Creation Tool the user can easily design both standard (operative) and training procedures, the latter being aimed at simulated sessions for learning purposes.

The basic concepts into authoring a training procedure are the following:

Resources: resources are the items the user can involve in your procedures, such as instruments, materials, spares. But the user can use resources as descriptive assets in order to illustrate how to perform a task.

Operations: operations are the top level parts a procedure can be split into. Each operation describes a task and a procedure is made of at least one operation.

Steps: steps are the stages required to perform an operation. They can describe concurrent or consecutive sub-tasks or stages that must be performed in some circumstances.

Actions: actions are the most detailed parts of the procedure, that is the very single tasks to be performed. There are 8 types of actions:

- **Assemble:** an action requiring two or more resources to be put somehow combined
- **Disassemble:** the action performing aiming at the opposite goal of the Assemble
- **Act:** this type of action refers to somehow interacting with something
- **Check:** the action requires the user to verify a situation or the condition of some resources
- **Measure:** the user is asked to calculate any feature of some item
- **Fill in:** an action requiring to write down some information, both on paper or using a device
- **Wait:** actions must be delayed for a specified amount of time or until a condition occurs
- **Move:** the user is asked to change the position of some resources or to move himself

Relations: relations are used to express how different parts of the procedure (i.e. Operations, Steps, Actions) are related to each other. There are 5 types of relations:

- **Consecutive:** the parts are intended to be executed sequentially
- **Contemporary:** the parts are required to be performed at the same time
- **Indistinct:** there is no restriction about the dependency between the parts

- **Repeated:** the task must be performed for a specified number of times
- **Conditional:** the task must be executed only if a specified condition occurs

5.1.1.2 Adding resources

The first thing to do in order to create a new training procedure is to include some training resources (Images, Videos, Audio, Documents etc.)

Figure 6 Accessing the Resources menu

Resources are collected in an inventory shared by all procedures. The inventory is stored locally on the computer running the AR OP Creation Tool, thus different workstations could provide different resources. The user can select how to browse the inventory by list view or grid view. The following Figure shows the grid view, while the next one shows the list view.

Figure 7 View resources as grid

Figure 8 View resources as list

The different types of Resources that can be added to a Procedure are as follows:

- **Videos, Images and Audio** are quite straightforward as they describe a resource (a tool, a task, ...) using movieclips, pictures or sounds saved in the most common file formats.
- **Texts and Documents** provide written descriptions about an item or informations about a task. The user can use .txt, .doc, .docx and other common filetypes.
- **3D Models** are complex three-dimensional representations of items and objects. They can include an animation representation of how the item works / how to perform an action.
- **AR Targets** are special sources (e.g. an image or an object) used to trigger interactive content when an AR⁺ (augmented reality) device is used to view the procedure.
- **Data Providers** are complex resources, saved in the special .dp file format, that are used to describe and provide access to devices and sensors available in the production environment.

In the inventory, resources are grouped by type: Video, Image, Audio, Text, Documents, AR Target, 3D Model, Data Provider and the user can also use the Search tool to find a resource inside the inventory by its name or part of it.

Figure 9 Resource preview window

Many of the resource types can be previewed in the inventory, double-clicking the resource. The example above shows the preview for a Video file.

Clicking the (+) button adds a new resource to the global repository. The user then, fills-in the fields in the detail panel and apply the changes.

5.1.1.3 Creating, Opening, Saving and Exporting Procedures

The **file** section lists the available Procedures, if any. It is also the first screen you see when the AR OP Creation Tool loads. In the Figure below, the user can see how a procedure appears in the file screen. This one is part of the Operative procedures. The user can use the pencil and trashcan icons to edit and to delete a procedure.

Figure 10 Procedure List UI

Clicking the (+) button starts creating a new procedure. Upon creating a new procedure, the user is asked to choose between training and standard operative procedure types.

Clicking the Save button allows to Save (or Save As...) the current procedure.

Using the file submenu the user can export a selected procedure or import an existing one (which has been previously exported). Upon selecting to export, the following Figure shows the UI presented to the user. The **export** button on the right initiates the exporting.

The user can choose among 4 export options:

- When exporting **AS PACKAGE** the user is publishing the release kit to be used by the AR OP Presentation Tool during the operative application of the procedure. The user will be asked to select the destination platform and if the procedure shall be available for GlassUp operation.

Figure 11 Exporting a procedure as Package

- When exporting **AS PROJECT** the user is creating a whole set in order to move the current procedure and its dependencies into another workstation. This is the export type required in order to perform a subsequent import operation. The user selects the target folder, names the exported project and inserts a password (required) to protect it from unwanted import.

Figure 12 Exporting a procedure as Project

- The user can choose AS IMAGE to export the visual summary of the procedure's graph.

Figure 13 Export as Image

- When the user exports the procedure **AS PDF**, a document is created including all the procedure's detail in a printable multi-page layout. Due to format restrictions, some information is not included, such as multimedia files preview. The user can customize the PDF document with a different header and logo.

Figure 14 Export as PDF

5.1.1.4 Adjusting Settings

Through the Settings panel the user can customize several aspects of the AR OP Creation Tool.

Figure 15 The Settings Panel

5.1.1.5 Overview of Training Procedures

Figure 16 The Project Interface

When editing a new or existing procedure, the home section opens and its submenu lets you access four areas: **Inventory**, **Project**, **My Resources**, **Play**.

Project offers you a graph view of the procedure tree, starting from its very root element. The user can use the project to add nodes to the tree, edit existing nodes or delete them and, more broadly, to create or modify the procedure itself.

- The **left panel** includes the tools the user can use to draw the procedure, i.e. the Operations, the Steps, the Actions and the Relations.
- The **main panel** contains the graph view of the procedure. The user can use the mouse wheel to zoom in/out and click on an empty area to drag and pan the view. Inside the main panel there is a **floating panel**. This floating panel allows the user to navigate the whole procedure view and to find out which part of the whole view is shown in the main panel. The user can choose to view the entire tree or to view only the nodes connected with the selected node.
- The **right panel** contains all the information about the selected node. At the beginning it displays the details about the procedure itself.

The authoring of a training procedure involves creating a graph of **Operations**, **Steps** and **Actions** by drag and dropping them from the left to the main panel and linking them with **Relations**. Then for each node, the relevant information and resources need to be defined in the right panel. The resources are added to **Action** nodes and form what we refer to as Descriptive layers.

Actions can be added to the procedure tree the same way other nodes are added. When adding an Action the user is asked to specify the type of action to be added and every type has its own meaning. Moreover, actions are described by a whole different set of details, including the so far unknown objects and descriptive layers.

Figure 17 Action Node Global Information panel

The first set of action's details is the same of other nodes. They are the so called Global info. The Expected Execution Time is part of action's peculiarities. The planned duration of the action is stated here, in a hh:mm:ss format.

Figure 18 Action Node Objects panel

Figure 19 Different Object types

Objects are the key elements used in the action and can belong to three types:

Items: they are the objects involved in the action as part of it, the "things" the action works on.

Objects to/from: resources listed under this classification are the "things" from or to other objects are moved.

Objects with: they are the tools used to perform an action, a movement, a regulation etc.

When an object is added to the action, detailed information is being added about the task performed by the action and how to perform it. To add an object, the user clicks on the desired type. The inventory will open, allowing the user to select the items to add. To add the items follows the same methodology as when adding resources to the inventory.

The Descriptive Layers are also very important in distinguishing the actions. They are used to attach to the action a number of resources describing how to perform the task. The Descriptive Layers are the part of the procedure where multimedia are used to provide the user a solid tutorial on how to perform a task.

Figure 20 The Descriptive Layers panel

The Descriptive Layers are attached to the action and consist in one or several files, ranging from basic text to complex 3D animations. They are meant to be consulted by the user and to implement an effective description of the operations representing the task. Please note that every single attachment is intended to be descriptive of the entire action, so the different Descriptive Layers should not be intended as portions of a "bigger picture" but rather as alternative descriptions of the same task. They are different point of view on the same routine, e.g. a movie showing the task sequence and a text describing it.

The supported types for Descriptive Layers are the following:

Text: one or more basic text documents describing the task.

Document: similar to the text layer, this one refers to structured files, such as PDF documents.

Audio: one or more audio recordings where (typically) a voice explains the action and how to perform it.

Video: the same as the Audio layer, but in the form of one or more videoclips.

Image: one or more pictures showing the distinctive traits of the action.

Animation 3D: one or more files presenting a three-dimensional simulation of the objects and of the action itself. It can be interactive.

Figure 21 Textual Descriptive Layers

Figure 22 Image Descriptive Layers

The Textual descriptive layer can be edited inside the AR OP Creation Tool (Value) or by choosing to load text files from the global Resources repository. Only the Text type resources shall be listed when the user accesses the repository. The added text will appear in the lower portion of the screen, as a single item.

Other types of the Descriptive Layers, such as the Images, cannot be edited inside the AR OP Creation Tool so the users have to choose if they want to load a file from their computer (File System) or from the global Resources repository. The resources repository will be filtered by the corresponding resource type (Image, in this case).

Figure 23 3D Model Descriptive Layers

Figure 24 Assigning AR Target to Descriptive Layer

Each item of the Descriptive Layers can be associated to an AR Target. However, AR Targets are usually associated to 3D Models. AR Targets are a special type of Resources and can be found (and created) in the global resources repository. To specify an AR Target that will trigger the Descriptive item, click on the (+) button on the selected Descriptive Layer.

AR Targets can be of different types, the most common being the Image Target. They can also be recognisable frames surrounding an image (Frame Marker) or actual real-world objects (Object Target) and the user can define their property and load the required source files when editing the resource in the global repository. The ORS (Object Recognition System) format by CERTH can also be used. AR Targets are real-world items that can be recognised by specific Augmented Reality modules of the AR OP Suite, in compliance with the Augmented Reality (AR+) principles. When an AR Target is recognised, it can be used to trigger the visualization of a selected content, i.e. the Descriptive Layers' content of an action. Thus, the user can design the procedure so that when an AR Target – let's say a target image placed inside the production line – is visible, the appointed AR OP Tool shows a selected descriptive item.

Figure 25 Conditional Relations

Conditions can refer to **Devices** or to **Text**. When a **Device** condition is selected, you are referring to a Data Provider that will be consulted at real-time to verify if a certain state is occurring.

The **Text** condition allows to explicitly claim what is going to be tested, describing it in the specific text field. The user should verify personally the described condition to determine if the conditional action has to be performed or not.

In both cases, the user selects the test operator (bigger than, minor than, equal to, different from) and insert the value you want to compare to. The user can manually insert the value (Manual) or refer to a Setting or a Device, where relevant. The condition can be tested once or repeatedly until the test is successful. In the first case, the condition is controlled and if it fails the related action (or node) is not considered. Instead, if the test is successful, the related node is considered. In the latter case, the procedure doesn't ignore the node if the condition fails, yet the node (or action) is

performed as soon as the condition occurs (if ever). The users can select the Wait until checkbox if they want to activate the second behaviour.

5.1.1.6 Training Procedures

Training Procedures are very similar to Standard Operative Procedures, but they have some distinguishing features:

- **Survey Action type:** In addition to standar action types, when you are building a Training Procedure you can benefit from this special action node type. It's meant to add a specific "survey" file format as a descriptive layer, in order to implement questionnaires and similar tasks during a training session.
- **Forced values in the condition editor:** When the user is designing conditional relations inside a Training Procedure and the condition is based on a device status, the user can impose a specific value instead of a run-time detection of the value. This allows the user to design training procedures with stable and predefined scenarios.

Figure 26 Creating a Training procedure

Figure 27 Adding a Survey Action type

5.1.1.7 Training Sessions

Training sessions are groups of procedures to be executed in sequence as part of a regimen. To create new Training Sessions or manage existing ones the user selects the **Training** submenu from the main menu and then clicks the (+) button to create a new session.

Figure 28 Adding procedures to a Training Session

When all desired procedures are added to a Session, the Training Session is complete and ready to be published. The user can still edit or delete it by clicking the upper right icons. Please note that, in order to accurately publish the Training Session, the user needs to pre-emptively export each included procedure as package. The exported Training Session doesn't include the procedures' content but only a reference to it.

A detailed step by step tutorial on how to author a simple procedure is included in Section 6.

5.1.1.8 Resources Added to a Procedure

My resources section lists all the resources currently being used in the procedure. It is a subset of the global resources loaded in the AR OP Creation Tool. If a resource is in the My resources section, it is also included in the global resources archive. Please note that the user can't edit, delete or add resources in the my resources section, yet the user can preview most of the resource types. The user must use the global Resources section to modify the resources.

Figure 29 The My resources section

5.1.1.9 Previewing a procedure

The **Play** section allows the user to navigate the whole procedure tree starting from the root node until the entire procedure is completed and check the correct sequence of steps. The procedure is shown step by step, node by node. For each node (action) the detailed information are shown, as well as the *objects* involved and the *descriptive layers* included. (please note that *objects* and *descriptive layers* are described later). The user starts by click the Initialize button to prepare the navigation. Then presses the Play button to begin and then uses the arrows to proceed to the previous / following node.

Figure 30 Play Section overview

Figure 31 Navigating through the procedure Nodes

5.1.1.10 Creating an inventory

In order to build-up a new procedure, the user should start creating an inventory, that is made of:

- Components
- Equipment
- Tools

The user is free to define what is a component, what is an equipment unit and what is a tool and what every category means according to the user's procedure's nature and semantic.

Every inventory item (a component, a part of the equipment, a tool) is made of none, one or several resources selected from the global resource repository and its described by:

- Code: an alphanumeric sequence used to univocally identify the item.
- Name: the friendly name of the item.
- Short description: a brief summary of the item's features.
- Description: the extended description of the item's features.
- Amount: use this field to specify how many copies of the item are involved in the procedure.

The inventory is accessible from the home submenu when a procedure is being created or edited.

Figure 32 The Inventory section

The user can add new items by clicking the (+) icon. For each item using the buttons on the right of the item panel, allows to edit or delete the item, while the number of items of the same type is highlighted in the item's summary

5.1.2 AR On-the-Job Training Presentation Tool

5.1.2.1 Purpose and features

The AR OP Presentation Tool is a multi-device software running on Mobile Devices, AR Glasses and more. It grants factory workers and other workmen the possibility to learn or follow job procedures using:

- Pictures
- Audio
- Video
- Interactive 3D Models

- Augmented Reality Content

Using the AR OP Presentation Tool the user can easily consult interactive procedures when involved in on-the-job activities or simulated environments. The target applications of the tool are:

- Training
- Assembly
- Maintenance
- Planned Activities
- Emergency Situations

The AR OP Presentation Tool runs on an interactive device (i.e. a tablet or an AR+ device) and presents a working procedure you can navigate through and consult while working or during a training session.

Procedures are made up of few important elements as seen in 5.2.1:

- Operations
- Steps
- Actions
- Relations

5.1.2.2 Working with the Presentation Tool

After the application launch, the user enters login information as required and inserts the Session information, as well as selects if the procedure will be used on a GlassUp device.

Figure 33 Login Interface of the Presentation Tool

The user can choose between two session types: Production sessions are intended to occur as on-the-job guided sessions. Training sessions are intended as learning sessions. Please note that the required data differ for the two types. When all the information have been inserted, the user can press the "Play" button to start using the AR OP Presentation Tool.

Then the list of available Production procedures or Training sessions according to the user's selection in the login interface is presented where the user can select the desired one. The user can swipe right or left to see all the listed procedures or sessions.

Figure 34 Selection of Procedure or Training Session

Upon selection of a procedure or session, the interface changes to the following:

Figure 35 Main Presentation Tool Interface

The top panel presents the navigation into the procedure. The current action along with its description and resources are displayed in the middle panel, while the icons on the bottom panel

allow the user to switch to different description layer types for the current action. In the previous figure, the objects and tools used in the action are presented, while in the figure below, the image descriptive layer for the action is displayed.

Figure 36 Image descriptive layer

The user can use the navigation buttons to follow the entire procedure's tree and all the listed actions, step-by-step.

- NEXT – Clicking this button proceeds to the next Action.
- PREVIOUS – Clicking this button returns to the previous Action.
- PAUSE – Clicking this button suspends the operation.

5.1.2.3 3D and Augmented Reality

3D and AR⁺ descriptive layers describe the Action to be performed in a very effective way, since they use 3D models and (for AR⁺) virtual representations of tools, items and actions mixed with surrounding reality.

3D content is based on interactive 3D models and animations that show the user the way the task is to be performed. The user can interact with the animation and view the model and the actions from any three dimensional point of view.

Augmented Reality (AR⁺) presents the 3D content and animations mixing them up with the images of the surrounding environment. Through the device camera or the smart glasses the user can see the 3D virtual model aligned and overlapping the real world objects. This allows the user to have a more precise description of how to perform the task. The AR⁺ content can be activated automatically by target images or predefined elements in the surrounding environment.

Figure 37 Selecting 3D or AR+ Descriptive Layers

Figure 38 3D Content (left) and AR content (right)

A detailed step by step tutorial on how to use the Presentation tool to follow a simple procedure is included in Section 6.

5.1.3 Shopfloor Management Platform

5.1.3.1 System Overview

Shop Floor Management Platform is a common tool which provides an interface for the combined functionalities of SatisFactory's HR Workload Balancing Toolkit and Maintenance Toolkit.

The HR Workload Balancing Toolkit is used to provide an intuitive interface which gives the possibility to analyse the factory at a glance. The benefits are manifold as all the notifications, alarms and unexpected behaviours are collected in a single entity. This allows for a prompt reaction to potentially dangerous events and quick re-adaptations of the previously scheduled tasks.

The HR Workload Management toolkit and the Re-adaptation toolkit are involved at several use cases. They provide in a single point of aggregation, heterogeneous information coming from the shop floor that can be used either for notifying users or as input for other toolkits or components the SatisFactory platform. The presentation and visualization of the heterogeneous data into one application is a useful tool for workers, especially for the supervisors and the decision makers who need to have as much information as possible gathered in order to take decisions with the optimal and fastest way.

The Maintenance Toolkit of the SatisFactory project is responsible to discover malfunction on the shop floors and trigger the most suitable maintenance process, predict a possible malfunction and alert workers to take measure to counteract against the malfunction before it happens, facilitate the daily work schedule, working together with the Human Resources Balancing Toolkit. Another functionality of the Maintenance Toolkit is to communicate with the Shop Floor Feedback Engine, concerning the maintenance tasks that happen on the shop floor. Finally, the Maintenance Toolkit is responsible to distribute messages about maintenance tasks to all the other SatisFactory components through CIDEM.

The UI for the Shop Floor Management Platform is design to improve ease of use, exploiting user – friendly capabilities and its simplicity.

5.1.3.2 Getting Started

Log in and main page of the Shop Floor Management Platform show an overview of the user interface and the credentials form.

Figure 39: Log in Screen

Only registered users can log in the platform. Username and Password are required to be completed in the form and a Log In button is present. If the credentials are correctly inserted in the form, user gain access in the platform.

Figure 40: Shop Floor Management Platform Main page

Figure 40 shows the main page of the platform. Graphs of tasks are present and the screen is called dashboard. On the dashboard, there is place for four graphs which are:

- Number of tasks per month
- New Tasks

- Delayed Tasks
- Performance Meter Template (PDD)

On the ribbon above the dashboard, short cut buttons with different functionalities are present. The buttons are called:

- Request – allows the user to create a new task
- Spare Part Order – allows the user to place an order for a new spare part.
- New Asset - allows the user to add a new asset in the system
- Task Catalogue – shows the tasks that already are created in the platform.
- Preventive Maintenance - allows the user to create a new preventive maintenance task
- Asset Search – searches the platform to find the respective asset
- Customise – reorders and adds graphs to the dashboard screen.

Finally, the menu bar on Shop Floor Management Platform’s main page has six drop down menus and their respective sub – menus.

On the right side of the screen the log off button and the user profile are situated, as seen on Figure 41

Figure 41: Log of and profile screen

Figure 42: Tree structure of the Shop Floor Management Platform

5.1.3.3 Tasks Menu

Tasks menu is the menu where all different functionalities about the tasks are managed. A new task can be created from the tasks menu with the help of the Request sub – menu. Also, tasks can start and finish with Start and End sub – menu, the task catalogue is visible as well as a calendar with all the existing tasks. Essentially, the task menu manages the tasks on the shop floor. As show in Figure 43 many of the sub – menus have their own sub – menus and the depth of the Shop Floor Management Platform tree depends on the functionality of each meny

Figure 43: Task menu

5.1.3.3.1 Tasks Menu - Request

Figure 44: New task screen

A new task is created by users and the screen is the one shown in Figure 44. New tasks need general data, such as: assets, category, kind, description. General data describe all the assets for a task. Tasks are addressed to: trade, department, and with criticality. Applicants are the responsible workers for each task and a short description of task and repairs are shown. Also, time and date are available. Finally, the attachments pane exists for all necessary attachments for each task.

5.1.3.3.2 Task menu – Catalog

No.	Application	Desir. Date	Description	Category	Topology	Asset Code	Asset Description	Status	Trades	Select
3	23/05/2017 10:00		Test the application	Preventive Maintenance		CO1	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+
2	21/02/2017 16:22		Missing power	Corrective action		CO2	Cabinet02	Open	Mechanic	+
1	21/02/2017 16:20		Short circuit	Breakdown		CO1	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+

Figure 45: Catalogue Screen

Catalogue screen shows all the tasks in the platform. Buttons on the ribbon can be used to open a new task, start or an already existing task, manage task or apply filter. This functionality is available when a task is selected as shown in Figure 45.

5.1.3.4 Task menu – Scheduling

Scheduling of tasks is essential for uninterrupted operations on the shop floor. The SatisFactory project implements the HR Workload Balancing Toolkit to schedule new and inferred tasks daily. HR Workload Balancing Toolkit is a backend toolkit and the Shop Floor Management Platform is the user interface for the toolkit

Figure 46: Calendar for the HR Workload Balancing Toolkit

User can check the program and accept the schedule automatically assigned by HR. They are able to adjust the defined schedule according to the needs of the working day/week/month by using drag and drop option within scheduling calendar.

5.1.3.5 Core data menu

Core data menu is the menu where assets, technicians and every other new value is inserted. All values needed for creating, managing, scheduling tasks are inserted from the core data menu.

Figure 47: Core data menu

Figure 47 shows the screen of Assets sub – menu of the core data. When an asset is chosen as it is shown, the user can edit it, deleted it or even apply filters for it. Clicking the New button on the ribbon allows users to insert a new asset in the Shop Floor Management platform.

5.1.3.5.1 Core data – New asset menu

Figure 48: New Asset Screen

New asset screen, Figure 48 shows two panes for data. The first one consists of the main data fields of the inserted asset. Code, Description, Asser Type, Topology, Status etc are some of the main data. The second pane consists of several tabs, are interchangeable and they provide a full description of the concerning asset. Schemas, specifications, locations, measurements, technical attributes and attachments are some of the tabs. Each tab contains many fields to be completed. The level of detail of the assets determines which fields are completed. Buttons on the ribbon can save the asset, delete or create a new one, show the dashboard etc.

5.1.4 Shopfloor Feedback Android App

5.1.4.1 System Overview

Shop Floor Feedback Engine is a mobile application developed for the SatisFactory project. Workers use the application on shop floor in order to receive or send notifications to other SatisFactory components, oversee the tasks they are responsible to complete during the day, check the schedule of their tasks and finally create new maintenance tasks, when they discover a malfunction or a problem on the shop floor.

Shop Floor Feedback Engine is one SatisFactory's components. The toolkit works in collaboration with HR Workload Balancing Toolkit and Maintenance Toolkit, as well as their combined User Interface platform: Shop Floor Management Platform. It is developed for Android devices and for the time being it only supports Android 5.0, although there is intension for further development and expansion to more OS and platforms.

5.1.4.2 Getting Started

Log in screen of the Shop Floor Feedback Engine is shown in [Figure 49](#)

Figure 49: Log in Screen for the Shop Floor Feedback Engine

Users log in the application using a username and a password. Only authenticated users are able to log in the application and use it. If the user is authenticated, loading data notification

Figure 50: Loading Screen

When the authentication process is completed, the application leads the user to its menu. It consists of four main menus: Declare, Start, Technicians, Exit as shown in [Figure 51](#)

Figure 51: Shop Floor Feedback Engine toolkit menu

Shop Floor Feedback Engine's tree diagram is shown below in [Figure 52](#)

Figure 52: Shop Floor Feedback Engine tree

Declare menu is responsible for declaring new tasks through the Shop Floor Feedback Engine Toolkit. Start menu is able to start a task, Technicians menu shows the technician that use the Shop Floor Feedback Engine Toolkit. Finally, with Exit menu users can exit the application and finish their session.

5.1.4.2.1 Declare Menu

Declare menu is used for declaration of tasks in the Shop Floor Feedback Engine. It consists of five different sub – menus and the three control buttons: Save, Save and Start and Cancel. The sub – menus are: assets, description, category, kind and photo as shown in [Figure 53](#), along with the control buttons. In the picture, the menu is in Greek, due to the locale settings of the mobile device.

Figure 53: Declare menu

Sub – menu Assets is the list with all the possible assets the user can choose of. Assets are inserted from the Shop Floor Management platform and the Maintenance Toolkit. Description sub – menu

exists for a description of the task. Category allows the user to choose the category of the category of the task and kind sub – menu shows what kind of user is responsible to complete the task. Finally, photo sub – menu allows users to take a snapshot of the malfunction on the shop floor and upload it on the Shop Floor Feedback Engine toolkit. [Figure 54](#) shows the above description Declare menu.

Figure 54: Assets and Kinds sub - menus of Declare menu

Declare menu tree is shown in [Figure 55](#)

Figure 55: Declare menu tree

5.1.4.2.2 Start menu

Start menu can start tasks or assets on the Shop Floor Feedback Engine toolkit. Users can tick either Assets or Tasks on the start menu and the tap on the desired element. Finally, the three control buttons: Start, Refresh and Back allow the user to either start a task or refresh it and even more to go back and decide for different assets or tasks as shown in [Figure 56](#)

Figure 56: Start Menu

5.1.4.2.3 Technicians Menu

Shop Floor Feedback Engine application third menu is the Technicians menu. As its name indicated, this menu is responsible for handling the registered technicians in the application. [Figure 57](#) shows the basic screen of the technicians' menu. The menu has two main functionalities. The + sign adds new technicians in the application and the back button goes back to the main menu of the Shop Floor Feedback Engine application.

Figure 57: Technicians Screen

5.1.4.2.4 Exit Menu

Exit menu is the last menu of the Shop Floor Feedback Engine application. Its function is to determine whether users want to exit the application and for positive answers to terminate the application and exit to the Android OS. A notification which asks if users are sure if they want to exit the application pops up on the mobile device screen and allows two choices: yes or no, as show in [Figure 58](#). It is noted again, that the language settings are in Greek, due to the locale settings of the mobile device.

Figure 58: Exit Menu of the Shop Floor Feedback Engine

5.1.5 VTDAT (Visual Training Data Analytics Toolkit)

5.1.5.1 System Overview

Visual Training Data Analytics Toolkit (VTDAT) is a SatisFactory toolkit designed to provide visual representation to the knowledge retrieved from the rest of the SatisFactory components and toolkits. Knowledge extraction and exploitation is essential to increase user satisfaction. The toolkit is an angular web application, which can standalone run on a web browser.

KPIs are used to extract knowledge from tasks created on Maintenance Toolkit, HR Workload Balancing Toolkit, Shop Floor Feedback Engine, Social Collaboration Platform and Shop Floor Management Platform. KPIs are based on criticality, worker performance, worker improvement, their position on the shop floor and their ranking. The extracted knowledge is represented with many different graphs which show the correlation between the KPIs and the graphical representation.

5.1.5.2 Getting Started

Visual Training Data Analytics Toolkit runs on a web browser though the application does not need an internet connection to show results. It is built as a web application only for reason of ease of use and friendly user interface.

Figure 59: Initial Screen of the VTDAT

Figure 59 shows the initial screen of the toolkit. On the left side pane, the connected user is shown and their currently position on the shop floor. Below, the toolkit's tree is available. Each heading represents a new screen and different visuals of the extracted knowledge through KPIs. The right-side pane which covers most of the page shows the personalised first screen of the toolkit, according to the users' preferences. On Figure 59, a personalised message with daily news and project's process in higher on the screen. Below it data reports, news feed, daily calendar and comments and tweets cover the lower section of the screen. On the upper right corner of the screen, the preferred languages of the toolkit and the login mechanism are present.

Figure 60: VTDAT tree

Figure 60 shows the tree representation of the Visual Training Data Analytics Toolkit. The toolkit has two menus Dashboard and Graphs. Dashboard menu leads to Dashboard v.3 sub – menu, while the Graphs sub – menus are Training KPIs and Test.

5.1.5.3 Dashboard Menu

Dashboard menu leads only to the Dashboard v.3 sub – menu. The dashboard shows graphs of the total score of a trainee over time. Panes of the hours spent on training exist. The hours are measured on a daily, monthly and annual basis. On the lower section of the screen two panes which show the scheduled training sessions and a timeline of training sessions which covers a user defined period. [Figure 61](#) is the screen of Dashboard v.3 of menu Dashboard of the Visual Training Data Analytics Toolkit.

Figure 61: Dashboard v.3 of the VTDAT

5.1.5.4 Graphs Menu

5.1.5.4.1 Training KPIs

Training KPIs sub – menu shows the graphics which represent the performance of a trainee and their improvement over time.

Figure 62: Trainee Graphs for the VTDAT

The first two graphs of Dashboard v.3 sub – menu, [Figure 62](#), present the score a trainee achieves over time. During a year a trainee’s scores changes and depends on the tasks the trainee performs, whether they are familiar with the task, or even like it, whether they have help on the task etc. these KPIs offer a sum and the sum is the worker’s overall score. The second graph of [Figure 62](#) shows the trainees distribution according to experience levels. Trainees are novice, intermediate and expert and as the graphs shows the distribution is reverse with experience.

The final graph of sub – menu Training KPIs in [Figure 63](#), shows how a trainee is improved according four KPIs: trainee score, tasks, experience and trainee time. The four-axis graph shows the dependency of the experience to these four KPIs. Area coverage increases with experience and reaches maximum coverage when a trainee becomes and expert.

Figure 63: Overview Chart

5.1.5.4.2 Test

Test sub – menu is designed to contain all the possible graphs a user can choose to present the knowledge extracted from all used KPIS. [Figure 64](#), [Figure 65](#), [Figure 66](#) show the most commonly used graphs: simple line chart, line scatter diagram, stacked bar chart, horizontal bar chart, simple pie chart, gauge chart. Specialised charts and graphs according to the toolkit’s users are also able to be used.

Figure 64: Simple line chart and line scatter diagram

Figure 65: Stacked bar and horizontal bar charts

Figure 66: Simple pie and Gauge charts

5.1.6 Localization Manager (UWB Wearables)

The UWB-based Wearable Device (UWB-WD) is a wearable device with localization and/or ergonomics functionalities. It can be used mainly to support the safety and wellness of the workers in their working day when performing the daily activities. When the UWB-WD is used for localization, it can localize people in indoor environments (e.g. factory shop floor, warehouse, etc.). It allows other entities to trigger, automatically, an alarm whether they have discovered that someone is in an area which it is considered dangerous for people. It is worth mentioning that the UWB-WD will localize people only in specific areas (e.g. working environments with high risk of incidents), since it relies on UWB antennas, deployed in those areas, to localize. Therefore, a person wearing an UWB-WD only will be localized when it is in range with the aforementioned UWB antennas. On the other hand, when the wearable is used for ergonomics, it will monitor the people trunk posture. This manual will focus on describing how to use the UWB-WD for the localization functionality, in particular, for workers incident detection. The examples provided in this manual consider real scenarios in SUNLIGHT.

Figure 67: The Ultra-Wide Band (UWB)-based Wearable Device

5.1.6.1 Usage Scenarios

Figure 68 shows a top view map (60m x 20m) of one of the SUNLIGHT's shop floor in which they make battery production. The area in which the wearable device can be used to localize is a subset of this shop floor as it is shown in Figure 69. In addition, Figure 69 shows the coverage of the localization, according to the deployment of the UWB antennas, in which people are located. For this specific SUNLIGHT shop floor, it has been identified *a priori* the dangerous zone presented in Figure 70. This zone is virtually defined by other SatisFactory entities. In this case, it is considered as a well-known dangerous area by the people working there. However, new forbidden areas could be generated dynamically because something unexpected has happened (e.g., a machine is overheated and their surroundings have become dangerous). The example, that will be provided, is going to be based on the fixed and well-known dangerous area.

Figure 68: SUNLIGHT shop floor map

Figure 69: Localization Zone and UWB antennas.

Figure 70: Virtual Dangerous Zone.

5.1.6.2 How to use it?

The device has to be turned-on and worn by the worker before starting to work. Afterwards, the worker can perform his activities as usual.

1. To turn on the device, the worker should push the button (ON/OFF) which it is shown in

Figure 71³.

Figure 71: Powering on.

2. The device is powered on since the green LED status.

³ Real devices have a cover with a hole to see the LED status.

Figure 72: Device powered on.

3. Now, the device should be worn by the worker⁴.

Figure 73: Device on the worker.

4. When workers are performing their daily activities, the device will track them in real-time once they are in the localization zone. The device LED status and the ON/OFF button will blink once per second when performing localization. In particular, the LED status blinks in blue colour while the ON/OFF button in green colour. Thanks to the blinking behaviour, the workers can notice when they are being localized. For instance, if the device remains fixed in one state, i.e. A or B; it means, the UWB-WD is not localizing since it is out of range from the fixed UWB antennas.

⁴ The position in the body will be selected by each end-User partner.

Figure 74: LEDs blinking behavior when performing localization.

5. When the workers finish their working day, they can remove the device and turn it off with the ON/OFF button. During the turning off process, the LED status will switch color five (5) times every 0.5 seconds (green, red, blue, green, yellow) to finally remain off.
6. Workers should put on charge the UWB-WD as indicated in Figure 75.

Figure 75: Charging the device.

5.1.7 AR Glasses

Figure 76 The GlassUp AR Glasses

The general operation of the glasses is the same as far as the wearer is concerned. Their operation involves simply wearing them and turning them on.

The back-end API of the glasses is responsible for what is displayed on them and this is administered via a dedicated interface in the Social Collaboration Platform.

The social collaboration platform of SatisFactory provides the necessary functionalities for the setup and management of the AR Glasses devices of the shop floor. An administrator user can add a new AR Glasses device or remove an existed one from the system through the web-based interface of the social collaboration platform. In case a new AR Glasses device has to be added to the system, a static IP network address has to be assigned to the device along with a unique ID that is used for identification. The dialog that is shown when a new device is added is depicted in the figure below.

Figure 77 Addition of AR Glasses device via the social collaboration platform

After the addition of an AR Glasses device, the supervisor or a user with administrator privileges can allocate the device to a specific employee or deallocate it first from an employee in the case another employee needs to be equipped with the AR Glasses, as shown in the following figure. Each AR Glasses device can be assigned to at most one employee at a given time. When the AR Glasses device is allocated to an employee, the device's ID is associated with the employee's ID which is already stored to the repository.

Figure 78 – Allocation of AR Glasses to a worker through the social collaboration platform

The AR glasses produced by GlassUp are used in three different use cases within Satisfactory:

- In-factory training and support of workers using a flexible learning platform
- Monitoring and online notification of abnormal events or alarms
- Remote assistance to workers on-the-job

5.1.7.1 In-factory training and support of workers using a flexible learning platform

The use of the AR glasses for in-factory training is achieved by exporting a training procedure from the AR OP Creation Tool with support for GlassUp (as demonstrated in 5.2.1.3).

When a training procedure is exported with GlassUp support, the information and descriptive layers that are assigned to each step and action of the procedure are displayed on the glasses instead of the tablet screen.

The interaction with the procedure (moving to next/previous step, changing Descriptive Layer type etc.) is handled either using the dedicated external control base or via the Gesture Control Manager.

Figure 79 The external control base

5.1.7.2 Monitoring and online notification of abnormal events or alarms

Using the notification platform, the employees are informed through the AR Glasses with information related to the specific incident that has occurred in conjunction with necessary information in order to respond accordingly. Highly critical incident events that affect the operation of the shop floor or the safety of employees are sent to all AR Glasses devices that are connected to the system and are allocated to workers. Other critical incidents or alerts notifications are sent only to the AR Glasses of specific personnel classes, such as supervisors. For instance, when a fall detection incident is detected by the depth cameras system, a notification which contains an image of the monitored location and the description of the incident will be created and send to the foreman or the supervisor's AR Glasses. An alert notification message that is sent to the AR Glasses can be a plain text message, a combination of image and text message, or an audio message.

When the use of the AR Glasses is combined with the use of the wearable devices that allow the identification of a worker, a notification event can be personalized and can be send only to the AR Glasses of the involving worker. An indicative use case scenario is about sending an audio notification alert to a worker upon approaching or entering an area which is marked as forbidden. In this way the worker will be notified that he is entering a forbidden area. This notification is part of the response strategies and initiates the dispatching of the follow-up activities and proper notification for the course of events is available to the worker.

5.1.7.3 Remote assistance to workers on-the-job

Remote assistance is an important use case that is applied at the shop floor, especially for maintenance operations, as it allows to address problems conveniently, in less time and without

suspending current work, due to the fact that a worker is not required to move away from his/her current position for receiving assistance. Furthermore, another advantage is that the worker can apply the suggested instructions immediately in case of a manual work since he has access to the information via the AR Glasses, without the need for carrying a portable device continuously. As a result, worker satisfaction is increased. The remote assistance use case involves various SatisFactory components such as the AR Glasses, the middleware and the social collaboration platform. In particular, a worker who is equipped with an AR glasses device can request remote assistance from a supervisor or an experienced worker using the social collaboration platform. Information between the two users is exchanged in real-time and as a result the supervisor can assess the situation remotely, for example from the office, and provide guidance and instructions to the worker.

Figure 80 Real-time video stream of the AR Glasses shown in social collaboration platform

5.1.8 Suggestions Platform

5.1.8.1 Overview

In the overview section, the user is able to see all suggestions in the system classified by category. If a category contains too much suggestions to fit on one page, a scrolling arrow will appear.

The user is also able to filter the suggestions by status. If the status button has a color, all suggestions with this status will be shown. If the status-button is grey, suggestions with this status will be hidden.

Figure 81 Adding a new suggestion

Figure 82 Using Filters

If the user wants to filter using specific keywords, they can use the search box.

Figure 83 Searching for key words

Figure 84 Detailed view of a suggestion

5.1.8.2 Detail-View

To see details of a specific suggestion, click on the suggestion in the Suggestion Overview. If you want to vote on a suggestion, click on the voting buttons next to the votes. The user can only vote once for each suggestion.

Within these views, the user can add/edit/delete suggestions, respond to collaboration requests and These operations are covered step-by step in detail in Section 6.

5.1.9 Digital Andon/Gesture Control Management

5.1.9.1 System overview

The Digital Andon St is a web-based application designed to provide the Smart Assembly Station operators the appropriate instructions and schematics to improve the assembly process workflow. It is specifically thought for environment where users don't have easily access to traditional input devices due to safety gear (e.g. gloves). For this reason, the interface (section 5.1.9.3) can be completely controlled by contactless gestures (section 3.3.9) that guarantees a seamless interaction between a user and a machine. The former simply moves his body and the latter reacts accordingly.

In particular, through the Digital Andon St, the operators can browse assembly instructions and make or receive audio calls with supervisors when more specific assistance is required.

Section 5.1.9.2 reports the steps necessary to launch the application and to prepare or update the instruction sets displayed by the Digital Andon St.

5.1.9.2 Getting started

Each Smart Assembly Station is equipped with the following devices:

- The Digital Andon St software provided with a portable NUC (Next Unit of Computing) (see Figure 85).
- A Microsoft Kinect sensor to feed the system with a visible and an infrared video streaming.
- A speakerphone or an headset with microphone for audio communication.
- A screen to display the Digital Andon St interface.

Figure 85 Next Unit of Computing portable device

The user interface will automatically displayed on the Smart Assembly Station screen when the NUC device is turned on. Section 5.1.9.2.2 describes how the system can be controlled by operators.

5.1.9.2.1 Working mode

This section describes the two working modes available for the Digital Andon St: **default mode** or **directory mode**. Choose one mode rather than another influences both the Digital Andon St instructions sets structure and the user interface (see chapter 5.1.9.3).

The default mode suits to most of the Smart Assembly Stations assembly processes where the operators have to follow a single procedure consisting of multiple steps. On the other hand, the directory mode is thought for Smart Assembly Stations that can accomplish multiple assembly processes for different purposes. In this case the operator should be able to switch between different instructions at once.

The Digital Andon St accepts three types of instructions files formats detailed in the table below:

Content	Extensions
Images	png, jpg/jpeg, gif or bmp
Documents	pdf
Videos	mp4, ogg, webm

The server auto detects the format from the files extensions to properly load the contents. Files with unknown extensions are automatically skipped.

These files are always displayed in alphabetical order and must be organized in specific **instructions sets** which structure depends on the chosen working mode. The default mode require two instructions sets for each Smart Assembly Station:

- **Standard instructions set:** a sequence of files describing, step-by-step, the assembly process of the station.
- **Assistance instructions set:** a sequence of files provide additional assistance to the operator featuring for example, more detailed instructions.

Each set is stored inside a specific directory defined at installation time.

On the other hand, the directory mode instructions files must be contained underneath a single directory and its subdirectories (an example is depicted in Figure 86). The root directory path is defined at installation time.

Figure 86 : Example of directory tree structure

It is worth noting that the Digital Andon St software is installed without pre-installed instruction sets. These latter must be provided accordingly to the assembly process which will take place in the station. Instructions files and directory (other than the root) can be also added or deleted at runtime but after each change the interface must be refreshed (i.e. F5 key) to load the new information.

5.1.9.2.2 Application control

In order to start controlling the Digital Andon the operator must enter the Smart Assembly Station facing the Kinect sensor. For better results, the ideal operator distance is 2-3 m. The gesture detection could work even with greater or lower distances but with lesser accuracy.

The Digital Andon St is intended to be used only by one operator at a time; if other workers are present in the Smart Assembly Station they cannot interact with the system. Any occlusion between the operator and the sensor may produce inaccuracies in the gestures detection and should be avoided.

5.1.9.3 User interface

Two different interface templates are available depending on the selected working mode. The **standard mode template** (Figure 87) can be divided into three main areas:

- on the center part of the screen, label 1 refers to the area where instructions are displayed;
- on the top, label 2 marks the main bar reporting the instruction set (standard or assistance) and the current browsing progress;
- on the top right, label 3 marks the icon which provide the status of the audio call service.

Figure 87 Digital Andon St default mode template

This interface is designed to reset to the initial instruction when the operator leaves the station.

The **directory mode template** (Figure 88) can also be divided into four main areas:

- the center part of the screen, label 1, is quite similar to the previous one providing an area where instructions are displayed;
- on the top, label 2 marks the main bar reporting the current directory and the current browsing progress;
- on the top right, label 3 marks the icon which provide the status of the audio call service;
- on the left, label 4, a navigation panel (displayed at each user interaction) provide an overview of the current position in the instructions tree. Each directory, if not empty, appears a branch while instruction files are shown as leaves. The currently displayed instruction is highlighted with orange colour.

Figure 88 Digital Andon St directory mode template

The following table describes the meaning of each of the available icon of the navigation tree:

Icon	Content type
	Directory
	Empty directory
	Image
	Document
	Video

5.1.9.4 Gesture Control Management

To control the Digital Andon St interface, the operator can use various gestures for both instructions browsing and audio communication management. To correctly classify gestures the operator should be facing the Kinect sensor of the Smart Assembly Station with the poses discussed in the sections below (6.1.9.1 and 6.1.9.2).

The Figure 89 illustrates the avatar of an operator facing the sensor that will be used hereafter to describe the gestures. The operator is facing the sensor so the right side of the avatar (labeled with character “R”) is located to the left side of the document. On the contrary, left side is labeled with the character “L”.

Figure 89: Operator avatar

The detected gestures could have different meaning depending on the working mode below.

Gestures summary

Gesture	Standard mode	Directory mode
	Move to the next instruction of the correspondent set	Move to the next instruction of the correspondent set
	Move to the previous instruction of the correspondent set	Move to the previous instruction of the correspondent set
	Switch between standard and assistance mode	Go down in the directory tree accessing files nested under a specified folder
	Start a call or accept an incoming one	Start a call or accept an incoming one
	End an ongoing call or reject an incoming one	End an ongoing call or reject an incoming one

A detailed tutorial on how to use the supported gestures in each application that supports them is included in Section 6.

5.1.10 Social Collaboration Platform

5.1.10.1 Welcome page

After registering in the platform the user can login in order for the content to be personalized. (Figure 90). When clicking “register” button the user fills name, email, password, gender, type and date of birth. (Figure 91) A pre-defined list of types of employees have been designed according to the factory needs. (Figure 92)

Figure 90: Social Collaboration Platform, Login Page

The registration form is titled "Register" and includes the following fields and options:

- First name *
- Last name *
- Email *
- Password *
- Gender: Male
- Type: Floor Manager (dropdown)
- Qualification: Novice (dropdown)
- Job description *
- Birthday: 23/03/2017 (calendar icon)
- Buttons: CANCEL, REGISTER

Figure 91: Social Collaboration Platform, Registration Page

Figure 92: List of various types of employees

5.1.10.1 Personal Page

Tips & tricks provide the possibility to the users to ask and offer help. Network offers the possibility to the users to grow their network by viewing and adding co-workers. Home button gives the possibility to the users to view the network activities. This means that the users can view users' activities once they are posted (timeline). My profile button leads the user to the personal summary page. Once the user is logged in, he is notified for incidents, gamification news, co-workers requests, messages and general news of the network. (Figure 93)

Figure 93: Social Collaboration Platform, Personal Summary Page

5.1.10.2 My Profile page

Achievements consists of four sub sections: status, awards, challenges, in the crowd. Status gives the information that the user needs concerning the points, level, games and tasks completed (Figure 94). The Awards section informs the user analytically with regard to the awards earned (Figure 95). Challenges is the games available for the user to participate. In this section user can join a game or leave clicking on the “join button” or “leave button” respectively (Figure 96).

Figure 94: Gamification Status Page

Figure 95: Gamification Awards Page

Figure 96: Gamification Satisfactory Components' games

In “Personal” section (Figure 97) user can fill and edit the personal information such as CV, type of employee (Figure 98), gender, nationality (Figure 99), date of birth (Figure 100), residence, e-mail and phone number.

Figure 97: Personal Details Page

Figure 98: Types of Employees

Figure 99: List of Nationalities

Figure 100: Calendar View for DOB

Action Wall consists of videos and photos of the user (Figure 101). Whether the user views videos or photos with a mouse over can view information like title and views (Figure 102), as well as can edit or delete current video or photo (Figure 103-Figure 107). By clicking on “Add” button user can upload a video if the current section is “video of me” and a photo if the current section is “photos of me” (Figure 108 and Figure 109). User can upload a video from YouTube, from pc and upload a video on YouTube.

Figure 101: Action Wall (Videos, Photos of me)

Figure 102: View Photo Information

Figure 103: Edit / Delete Video

Figure 104: Edit Video

Figure 105: Edit Photo

Figure 106: Delete Video

Figure 107: Delete Photo

Figure 108: Add a Video

Figure 109: Add a Photo

Achievements, Personal, Action Wall, Connections, Timeline

In connections section user can view personal connections, followed and connected co-workers (Figure 110). Also can find connections through search tool and filter the results viewing all connections, co-workers, following and followers (Figure 111).

Figure 110: View all Connections

Figure 111: View Connections Filters

Personal timeline shows the users actions. User can add a post, which can be text, video or photo (Figure 112).

Figure 112: Add a Post

5.1.10.1 Home page

In this section, a timeline is available which consists of the posts that the user's network publishes. User can view posts (Figure 1134). Clicking on them user can view details like "like", "share" and "add a comment" (Figure 114: Like, Add, Share a Post, Figure 114). Like on personal timeline post with text video and photo is available. Posts can be published on co-workers, public, or private (Figure 115). Video can be uploaded from YouTube or pc and can be uploaded on YouTube or in the platform (Figure 116, Figure 117, Figure 118). A post consists of its title, description, date & time. User can edit the post, add a comment, delete, edit or like a comment. Also, one can share the whole post or like it (Figure 119). Clicking on "share" button, the user can publish the post to the personal timeline, to a co-worker's timeline or can send it via messenger (Figure 120).

Figure 113: View Posts

Figure 114: Like, Add, Share a Post

Post text [X]

Title
Need help - shop floor

Body
Need a hand in shop floor to lift a package. By error handling the calibration must be done manually.
2 pairs of hand needed.

Privacy
Public

POST

Figure 115: Publish a Post

Add a Video [X]

INSERT YOUTUBE LINK UPLOAD TO YOUTUBE LOCAL UPLOAD

Video URL*
<https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=YHc5SJrJig>

Title*
Best Hans Zimmer Music (Top 10 HD)

Description
▶ Subscribe: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCvgQ2_d_jFhX3uGNn_BHqcg
▶ More Videos: https://www.youtube.com/channel/UCvgQ2_d_jFhX3uGNn_BHqcg/playlists

Users tagging
John Deere [X] ...type a name

Privacy
Public

I have read and agree with the terms of use.

POST VIDEO

Figure 116: Add a Video (Insert YouTube Link)

Add a Video [X]

INSERT YOUTUBE LINK **UPLOAD TO YOUTUBE** LOCAL UPLOAD

CHOOSE VIDEO TO UPLOAD Video file*

Title*

Description

Users tagging
 John Deere x ...type a name

Privacy
 Public

I have read and agree with the terms of use.

POST VIDEO

Figure 117: Add a Video (Upload To Youtube)

Add a Video [X]

INSERT YOUTUBE LINK UPLOAD TO YOUTUBE **LOCAL UPLOAD**

CHOOSE VIDEO TO UPLOAD Video file*

Title* Please fill out this field.

Description

Users tagging
 John Deere x ...type a name

Privacy
 Public

POST VIDEO

Figure 118: Add a Video (Local Upload)

Figure 119: Edit, Like a Post

Figure 120: Share a Post

5.1.10.1 Network page

In this section, the user can grow his personal network by searching for co-workers to connect or follow. For this reason, a searching tool is available (Figure 121). A filter referring to the type of employee facilitates the user's searching (Figure 122). By clicking on the right button, the user can follow co-workers, connect with them, unfollow and disconnect (Figure 123).

Figure 121: Searching Tool

Figure 122: Employee Type Filter

Figure 123: Follow/Unfollow, Connect/Disconnect

5.1.10.2 Tips & Tricks page

In this section, the user can view all of the questions, ask a question and view personal activity concerning tips & tricks (Figure 124). In the Questions section can view a question using the searching tool and the filter viewing the “recently asked” questions or the most “popular” (Figure 125). By clicking on a question, the user can view the title and the description of the question, the votes, and the answers and can edit the question or answers, vote or comment an answer (Figure 126). Additionally, the user can also add an answer on the current question (Figure 127). In “Ask a question” section, the user can post a question in tips & tricks writing a title, a description and choosing a topic for the question (Figure 128). In “My activity” section, the user can view personal questions and answers with their features (Figure 129).

Figure 124: View All Questions

Figure 125: “Recently Added”, “Popular” Filters

Figure 126: Votes, Edit a Question, Post an Answer

Figure 127: Answer a Question

Figure 128: Post Your Question

Figure 129: My Activity

5.1.10.3 User Settings Page

All settings for notifications can be seen in the user profile choice “Settings” where the user can manage the customizations that are applied to her profile. First interface shows the settings that concern the personal account (Figure 130).

Figure 130 Account Settings

In the same interface, clicking on Privacy button leads to the privacy settings which allow the determination of what is private and what is public in the user's profile. The following figure shows the available changes in settings (Figure 131)

Figure 131 Privacy Settings

Finally, in Notification tab, the user can manage how she is going to be notified for every action that takes place in the social platform. In Figure 132, most of the choices are shown,

Figure 132 Notifications' Settings

This way profiles become more personal and customizable according to the preferences of each user. Moreover, users feel safer by having the ability to manage their security and privacy.

5.1.11 Gamification Platform

5.1.11.1 Gamification Administrator Interface

- The administrator of the platform has access to the gamification interface where she can create the gamified processes. This general Gamification engine, gives the opportunity to award any task with points, awards and levels. The engine supports creation of a game that can have one or many actions each one of them combined with a rule that determines if it is accomplished or not. For every accomplished task, an award can be assigned to the player's profile which can be an amount of points or a set of points and badges and after having collected some of them the experience level changes too, denoting more advanced knowledge. More features that are supported in the Gamification framework are:
 - Teams
 - Registration as a category of player
 - Quests
 - Leaderboards
 - Tangible Objects as awards
 - Ability to create a game for specific team or category of player
 - Ability to create rules for specific teams of categories of players
 - Gamification history element that tracks the actions triggered

- Levels

The user starts by registering to the gamification platform as well as she has done in social collaboration platform, but she has to register like administrator.

User can register exclusively as specific category provided from the Platform and denote level of experience concerning the platform's usage. (Figure 133)

The screenshot shows a 'Register' form with the following fields and options:

- First name *
- Last name *
- Email *
- Password *
- Gender: Male
- Type: Floor Manager (dropdown)
- Qualification: Novice (dropdown)
- Job description *
- Birthday: 23/03/2017 (calendar icon)
- CANCEL and REGISTER buttons at the bottom.

Figure 133 Register form

5.1.11.2 Creation of a game

- Choose if it is a game either for teams or for Individuals (Figure 134)

The screenshot shows a 'Create A Game' form with the following fields and options:

- Title *
- Description *
- Individual (selected) / group (radio buttons)

Figure 134 Create a Game

In Figure 135 the administrator can see all the existing games.

Figure 135 View all games

If a game is made for individuals then there is the ability to choose for what type of individual is designed (Figure 136)

Figure 136 Individual Categories

A game can be made also for team playing so the administrator should choose the team that is referred to. (Figure 137)

Figure 137 Team Categories

Teams are created before creating the game in order to have team list. To create a game one should give a name and a description in the appropriate forms. (Figure 138, Figure 139)

Figure 138 Create Team

Figure 139 Update Team

Afterwards, actions should be added by giving a name and a description and defining if the action is endorsing or not the player (Figure 140)

Figure 140 Add Action

Actions can also be Quests, so from the list of actions, one can be chosen and become quest with starting and ending date.(Figure 141)

Figure 141 Quests

In the meantime, awards must be created to in order to combine them with actions at rule engine forms. Awards can be of three types, there are the scalar type awards (Figure 142), the set awards (Figure 142) and levels (Figure 144).

Figure 142 Scalar award

Figure 143 Set Awards

The screenshot shows the 'Create A Level' form in the Satisfactory admin interface. The form is titled 'Create A Level' and is located within a user interface that shows 'User: admin' and a trophy icon. The form contains several fields: a 'Title' field with a checkmark icon, a 'Description' field with a document icon, a 'Level Start Point' field with a plus icon (circled in red), and a 'Hint' field with a checkmark icon. At the bottom right of the form, there are two buttons: 'CANCEL' and 'CREATE'.

Figure 144 Level Award

In level's form the administrator can write a hint in order to help with the acquisition of it.

Now actions and awards should be combined so that the game can have specific context and defined aim. The rules can be of two types:

- Rule for defining what the user gains after having completed an action for N times (Figure 145)
- Rule for defining what badge or level the user may gain by having collected N scalar values (points, coins etc)

Create A Rule

Title *

Description *

Relate to a Category
 no

TRIGGERED N TIMES HAS THE AWARD

Select An Action

equal to

times
 + 0

WINNING THE AWARD

Select an Award x 1

Figure 145 Rule for triggering an action N times

In Figure 146 the form of setting a rule provides the ability to set rules for either specific group of people or everyone. So the rule may apply to every player or to player that belong to a group e.g. Maintenance Supervisor.

Update Rule

Title *

Rule for asking a question

Description *

The rule that defines what the player gains for asking one question

Relate to a Category
 yes

Group
 Maintenance Supervisor

Triggered N Times Already has the Award

Action
 Ask Question -

Operator
 equal to

Times
 + 1

Winning Award

Award
 Point x 20

This Award is Type of Point with Value: 1

CANCEL ✕ UPDATE ↻

Figure 146 Rule for Maintenance Supervisor

Figure 147 Rule Set for gaining Set Awards

In Figure 147 the rule defines that player gains award according to how many points she has. Moreover, there is the ability to select a specific group of people that the rule is going to be applied, like the previous one.

Administrator has the overview of the rules in the main profile of the game when clicking on Rules from the menu on the left (Figure 148).

Figure 148 Rule List

Every game has also a dedicated leaderboard that shows the performance of every player according to their scalar values gained so far (Figure 149).

Figure 149 Leaderboard

Furthermore, the game has participants which are shown in Participants table without any ranking, only to inform about the level of participation to the specific game (Figure 150).

Figure 150 List of participants to a Game

Afterwards, the administrator of the platform can set as many game as needed in order to improve engagement in daily jobs and all these games are going to appear in the profile of each user with the choice of Join attached near to each game (Figure 151).

Figure 151 List of available games

For every game that the user has already joined, the gained points appear next to its name. There is also the choice to Leave the game, although the gained points will not be erased. So even if the player leaves the game for some reasons, the gained points are going to be kept so that if she re-joins, her past gains appear again.

Finally, a great amount of points yields to gain set of awards. These gained awards are shown in profile, in the Achievements section. (Figure 152)

The screenshot shows the 'MY PROFILE' page in the SATISFACTORY application. The user is 'Administrator Administrator', an 'Automation Technician'. The page is divided into several sections: 'Achievements', 'Personal', 'Action Wall', 'Connections', and 'Timeline'. The 'Personal' section displays a list of awards:

Award	Award Description
Bronze Cup	Bronze Cup Item
bronze	bronze
bronze	bronze

On the right side of the profile, there is a vertical menu with options: Status, Awards, Challenges, and In the crowd.

Figure 152 List of gained awards

In “Challenges” there are the attached Quests for each user, where she accept or reject them according to her preferences, while “in the crowd” there is the cumulative ranking of all users of the platform but each user can see in a range of three teammates before and after her.

6. TRAINING SCENARIOS

6.1.1 On-the-Job Training Creation Tool

6.1.1.1 Scenario 1: Create a simple Procedure

Step 1: Create a new (blank) procedure

The screenshot shows the R3D.OP.Creator application window. The title bar reads "...: R3D.OP.Creator ...". The menu bar includes "file", "home", "training", "resources", and "settings". Below the menu bar, there are options for "LIST", "EXPORT", and "IMPORT". The main content area displays "Procedures: 1 on 1" and a list of procedures. The first procedure is "Operative (1)" with a thumbnail card. The card contains the following information:

BSC5.2 Steps 11-15	
Monday, July 18, 2016 5:07 PM	
	Last update: Tuesday, May 23, 2017 5:55 PM
Chemical Process and Energy Resources Institute	Version: 0.1
	Authors: CPERI

Below the screenshot, a blue callout box with a plus icon and a document icon contains the text "Create a new (blank) procedure..." pointing to a plus sign icon in the software interface.

Step 2: Fill in all the procedure information:

- Name
- Code
- Short description
- Description
- Pre conditions: note down any action that is to be performed before starting the procedure steps.
- Authors
- Goal: depict the objective of the procedure and what it's supposed to produce.
- Version

Step 3: Add Inventory items

Step 4: Add information and resources to inventory items

Step 5: Select resources to add

Step 6: Save inventory item

When you've finished, save the item or cancel the operation.

Please remember that you can also create an inventory item with no resource attached. However, be sure to describe it the best way possible.

Step 7: Continue for all items involved in the procedure

Remember to save the changes often!

Repeat the steps so that every inventory item is created and classified as tool, component or equipment. When the inventory is complete, return to the Project view.

Step 8: Start building the Procedure – Enter the root node information of the procedure

file home training resources settings
INVENTORY PROJECT MY RESOURCES PLAY

Operations
Operation

Steps
Step

Actions
Assemble
Disassemble
Act
Check
Measure
Fill In
Wait
Move

Relations
Consecutive
Contemporary
Indistinct
Repeated

Operative BSC-5.2A
BSC5.2.A Steps 11-15

ROOT

Add child nodes starting from the root element. Your goal is to create a tree based on the **Operation > Step > Action** paths describing the procedure.

Click on the **Operation** icon and drag it on the graph area to create your first node.

Name: Procedure.
BSC5.2.A Steps 11-15
Code: BSC-5.2A
Short description: standard procedure for starting up a pilot plant in order first to reduce startup time and second to avoid errors during the startup procedures increasing the safety and reducing stress.
Description: Application Scenario BSC-5.2 is about the critical start-up step of operating hydroprocessing pilot plants and involves the loading of the feed tank, as the first step of the overall experimental plan, which needs to be carefully performed to allow the optimal feedstock introduction in the downstream catalytic system.
Pre conditions: All parts of the pilot plant to be ready for startup. The process operators must be familiar with the involved technological equipment.
Operations: 0 Steps: 0 Actions: 0 Orphans: 1

Step 9: Add an Operation and fill the information of the Operation in the Project section

file home training resources settings
INVENTORY PROJECT MY RESOURCES PLAY

Operations
Operation

Steps
Step

Actions
Assemble
Disassemble
Act
Check
Measure
Fill In
Wait
Move

Relations
Consecutive
Contemporary
Indistinct
Repeated

Operative BSC-5.2A
BSC5.2.A Steps 11-15

Operation
Load Reactor

Fill in the node's details, so that the user can understand the goal of this part of the procedure.

OPERATION

Name: Load Reactor
Code:
Short description:
Description:
Pre conditions:

Step 10: Connect the root node with the Operation node with a Relation

file home training resources settings
INVENTORY PROJECT MY RESOURCES PLAY

Operations
Operation

Steps
Step

Actions
Assemble
Disassemble
Act
Check
Measure
Fill In
Wait
Move

Relations
Consecutive
Contemporary
Indistinct
Repeated

Operative BSC-5.2A
BSC5.2.A Steps 11-15

Operation Load Reactor

OPERATION
Name: Load Reactor
Code:
Short description:
Description:
Pre conditions:

Note that the two nodes are not connected.

You must specify a relation between the two nodes, i.e. a way the procedure goes from the root node to the first operation (Load Reactor)

Select the **Consecutive** relation, just clicking on the corresponding text.

This means that the "Load Reactor" operation is to be performed right after (consecutively) the beginning of the procedure.

file home training resources settings
INVENTORY PROJECT MY RESOURCES PLAY

Operations
Operation

Steps
Step

Actions
Assemble
Disassemble
Act
Check
Measure
Fill In
Wait
Move

Relations
Consecutive
Contemporary
Indistinct
Repeated

Operative BSC-5.2A
BSC5.2.A Steps 11-15

Operation Load Reactor

OPERATION
Name: Load Reactor
Code:
Short description:
Description:
Pre conditions:

In order to link the two nodes, click on the circle sticking out from the right of the root node (source), then click on the circle sticking out from the left of the operation node (destination). A connection line should appear if you clicked properly.

Step 13: Add a step to the operation

The screenshot shows the R3D.OP.Creator interface with a procedure path. The path starts with an 'Operative' node (BSC-5.2A) which is connected to an 'Operation' node (Load Reactor). This operation is then connected to two 'Step' nodes: '11. Press zero button on the scale' and '11. Open the 3-way valve'. The relationships are labeled '1 CONSECUTIVE' and '2 CONSECUTIVE'.

The 'STEP' configuration panel on the right includes the following fields:

- Name:** 11. Open the 3-way valve
- Code:**
- Short description:** Open the 3-way valve
- Description:** Open the 3-way valve
- Pre conditions:**

**You can create siblings whenever you want, in order to build complex procedure paths.
Note that, in case of siblings, the relations are ordered by number.**

The screenshot shows the R3D.OP.Creator interface with the same procedure path as above. The 'CONSECUTIVE' configuration panel on the right includes the following fields:

- Name:**
- Code:**
- Short description:**
- Description:**
- Order:** 2

Use the Order field to change the order for the siblings' relations.

**You can create siblings whenever you want, in order to build complex procedure paths.
Note that, in case of siblings, the relations are ordered by number.**

The screenshot shows the R3D.OP.Creator interface. On the left, a sidebar lists 'Operations', 'Steps', and 'Actions'. The main workspace displays a workflow diagram with nodes: 'Operative' (BSC5.2.A), 'Operation Load Reactor', and 'Step 11. Press zero button on the scale'. A blue callout box with a white arrow points to a node, containing the text: "To delete a node, right click on it and select Delete." On the right, a 'CONSECUTIVE' configuration panel is visible with fields for Name, Code, Short description, Description, and Order.

Step 14: Add an Action to the procedure

The screenshot shows the R3D.OP.Creator interface with the 'Act' action selected in the sidebar. The workflow diagram now includes an 'Act' node. A blue callout box with a white arrow points to the 'Act' node, containing the text: "The first set of action's details is the same of other nodes. They are the so called Global info." Another blue callout box points to the 'Expected Execution Time' field in the configuration panel, containing the text: "The Expected Execution Time is part of action's peculiarities. State here the planned duration of the task, in a hh:mm:ss format." The configuration panel on the right is titled 'ACTION' and includes fields for Name, Code, Short description, Description, Preconditions, and Expected Execution Time.

Step 15: Add descriptive layers to the Action

Step 16: Add AR Targets (if available) to a descriptive layer

... R3D.OP.Creator ... BSC-5.2A- BSC5.2.A Steps 11-15

file home training resources settings

INVENTORY PROJECT MY RESOURCES PLAY

Animation 3D descriptive layer management

Resources: 3 on 20

FILE SYSTEM RESOURCES

Model 3D (3)

Step 12 anim ✓ ✎ 🗑

Standard

Step 12 anim

step12

Step 15 anim ✓ ✎ 🗑

Standard

Step 15 anim

step15

Step 14 anim ✓ ✎ 🗑

Standard

Step 14 anim

step14

+ search ...

Selected items

No AR Target associated

Standard

To specify an AR Target that will trigger the Descriptive item, click on the button.

... R3D.OP.Creator ... BSC-5.2A- BSC5.2.A Steps 11-15

file home training resources settings

INVENTORY PROJECT MY RESOURCES PLAY

AR target management

Resources: 4 on 22

FILE SYSTEM RESOURCES

AR Target (4)

marker4 ✓ ✎ 🗑

Image Target

marker4

marker5 ✓ ✎ 🗑

Image Target

marker5

marker1 ✓ ✎ 🗑

Image Target

marker1

marker2 ✓ ✎ 🗑

Image Target

marker2

+ search ...

Selected Item

Select the desired AR Target clicking the button. The item will be added to the **Selected Item** area.

Please note that you can add only one AR Target per single Descriptive item.

Step 17: Connect the Action to the parent Step with a Conditional Relation

The screenshot shows the R3D.OP.Creator software interface. On the left, there is a sidebar with various actions and relations. The main workspace displays a workflow diagram with steps like 'Load Reactor' and '11. Press zero button on the scale', connected by arrows labeled '1 CONSECUTIVE' and '2 CONSECUTIVE'. A 'CONDITIONAL' configuration panel is open on the right, showing fields for Name, Code, Short description, and Description. Below these fields, there is a 'Condition Editor' with two conditions: 'Wait until Pressure value > 150' and 'Wait until Temperature < 200'. A blue callout box is overlaid on the diagram with the text: 'Insert as many Conditions as you want: they will be tested separately and the global condition will succeed only if all the subconditions will subsist.'

6.1.2 On-the-Job Training Presentation Tool

6.1.2.1 Scenario 1: Login, Start and follow a Procedure

Step 1: Enter Login information

The screenshot shows a 'SIGN IN' form with two main sections: 'Login information' and 'Session information'. The 'Login information' section includes fields for User (u001), Experience level (Novice), Role (Worker), Language (English), and a checkbox for Classup Support. The 'Session information' section includes a dropdown for Session type (Production) and a sub-section for 'Production information' with fields for Order n. (orderABC) and Shift (First). Three orange callout boxes provide instructions: 'After the application launch, insert your login information as required.' points to the User field; 'Check this box if you are going to use a Glassup device.' points to the Classup Support checkbox; and 'Insert the Session information required too.' points to the Session type dropdown.

Step 2: Enter session Information

SIGN IN

Login information

User:

Experience level:

Role:

Language:

Classup Support:

Session information

Session type:

Production information

Order n.:

Shift:

You can choose between two session types: **Production** sessions are intended to occur as on-the-job guided sessions. **Training** sessions are intended as learning sessions.

Step 3: Start the Presentation Tool

SIGN IN

Login information

User:

Experience level:

Role:

Language:

Classup Support:

Session information

Session type:

Production information

Order n.:

Shift:

When all the information have been inserted, press the "Play" button to start using the **AR OP Presentation Tool**

Step 4: Select the desired Procedure

Select the desired **Production Procedure** or **Training Session**.

You can swipe right or left to see all the listed procedures or sessions

Step 5: Upon loading a procedure take a look to the Action path to know how the task is involved in the whole procedure.

Step 6: Carefully read the description of the Action to be performed.

Step 7: Take a look at the Objects required to perform the current Action. You can swipe left and right to view all the items.

Remember that objects can be Items, Objects to/from or Objects with.

Step 8: Consult the Descriptive content.

Descriptive content is available in different content types (Descriptive Layers), each one illustrating the process in a different way. Available content types (e.g. Images, Documents, 3D Animations, ...) are coloured in red and can be selected touching the icon.

Step 9: View a descriptive layer

Swipe left or right to view all the content items.

To view one of the listed items, simply touch it and the device will show it. The way an item is displayed depends on the item's type and on the device's capabilities.

Step 10: Navigate the procedure step by step

Use the navigation buttons to consult the entire procedure's tree and all the listed actions, step-by-step.

1. NEXT – Click this button to go to the next Action.
2. PREVIOUS – Click this button to go back to the previous Action.
3. PAUSE – Click this button to suspend the consultation.

6.1.3 Shopfloor Management Platform

6.1.3.1 Scenario 1: Scheduling Steps with Maintenance Toolkit for Administrator

User (i.e. administrator) is responsible to create new tasks and provide all necessary information within Maintenance toolkit and iDSS. This way, the Standard Operating Procedure (SOP) is created, which is then visualized to the people at shopfloor level who are using the Shopfloor Feedback Engine. This is done by using the “Preventive/Schedules” functionality of the Maintenance Toolkit. iDSS and Maintenance toolkit must both be installed on a local PC that administrator is using.

Steps:

No. 1: Click on IDSS.exe application file (locally installed at users’ PC).

No. 2: Type “idss- schedule” in the command line and press enter.

No. 3: Open browser e.g. , and type local host IP <http://localhost/HomeNew/IndexNew>

No. 4: Click on menu “Preventive/Schedules” at the following page is displayed

Code	Description	Asset	Next Exec.	Remarks	Active
AIRCOMP-1M	6Μηνιαία συντήρηση αεροσυμπίστη	Αεροσυμπίστης Αφυδάτωσης	08/07/2014		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
1	Μηνιαία συντήρηση ψυκτήρα αστικών Β	Ψυκτήρας αέρα Αστικών	19/09/2013		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
2	Μηνιαία συντήρηση σωληνώσεων μεταφορικής ταινίας αφυδάτωσης	Μεταφορική 1 αινια Αφυδάτωσης Α	19/09/2013		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ScrAstA-1Y	Ετήσια Συντήρηση Εσχάρων Αστικών Α	Εσχάρα Αστικών Α	14/03/2014		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ScrAstA-1M	Μηνιαία Συντήρηση Εσχάρων Αστικών Α	Εσχάρα Αστικών Α	22/11/2013		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ScrAstA-6M	Εξαμηνιαία Συντήρηση Εσχάρων Αστικών Α	Εσχάρα Αστικών Α	14/09/2013		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ScrAstB-1M	Μηνιαία Συντήρηση Εσχάρων Αστικών Β	Εσχάρα Αστικών Β	14/10/2013		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ScrAstB-6M	Εξαμηνιαία Συντήρηση Εσχάρων Αστικών Β	Εσχάρα Αστικών Β	14/09/2013		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ScrAstB-1Y	Ετήσια Συντήρηση Εσχάρων Αστικών Β	Εσχάρα Αστικών Β	14/03/2014		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>
ConvAst-1M	Μηνιαία Συντήρηση συμπίεση εσχαρισμάτων Αστικών	Συμπίεστικός Κοχλίας Εσχαρισμάτων	14/10/2013		<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>

No. 5: Create new task by clicking “New” button. New task menu will be opened.

No.	Application	Desir. Date	Description	Category	Topology	Asset Code	Asset Description	Status	Trades
101	24/01/2017 15:06		Operators detect malfunction	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
100	24/01/2017 14:12		A malfunction happens to the	Malfunction			BIOCAT Liquid Feed Subsystem	Open	Chemical Engineer
98	24/01/2017 13:09		A malfunction happens at the	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
96	24/01/2017 12:43		Malfunction at the rooftop	Malfunction			CHU_EXT, CALIBRATION ROOM	Open	Chemical Engineer
94	24/01/2017 12:30		Malfunction at the Syngas	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
92	24/01/2017 12:20		A malfunction was detected	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
90	24/01/2017 12:06		A malfunction was detected	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Executing	Chemical Engineer
89	16/12/2016 12:06		new construction	New Construction			WING A', L307, VENT.UNIT	Open	Chemical Engineer
88	16/12/2016 12:03		malfunction	Malfunction	EKETA	testAsset	testAsset	Open	Electrical Technician
87	15/12/2016 13:27		test	Malfunction	EKETA	testAsset	testAsset	Open	Automation Technician

No. 6: Specify code, schedule description, the asset the schedule concerns, choose task category, schedule prototype, choose technician, estimate number of hours needed to execute the task and click “Save” button. *Note that instructions (click and type any text you want instructions to contain) and attach files if necessary. Click “Save” button at the end.*

No. 7: Repeat step No. 4 and check the new task at the top of the task list.

Once the SOP is created in this way, it can be extracted by the iDSS in case it is necessary to be provided at shopfloor level, via the Shopfloor Feedback Engine.

6.1.3.2 Scenario 2: Rebalancing Workload with HR Workload balancing Toolkit (**Administrator**)

The Administrator is responsible to create new tasks and provide all necessary information within Maintenance toolkit and iDSS. iDSS and Maintenance toolkit must be installed on a local PC that administrator is using.

Steps:

No. 1: Click on IDSS.exe application file (locally installed at users' PC).

No. 2: Type "idss- schedule" in the command line and press enter.


```
Select file:///C:/Users/charis/Documents/satisfactory/Src/IDSS/bin/Debug/IDSS.EXE
2017-01-31 10:29:53,100 [8] DEBUG ABE.IDSS.Program [(null)] - starting
Last task :112740
Total tasks:99-last task 112740-last completed 112740
```


No. 3: Open browser e.g. <http://localhost/HomeNew/IndexNew> , and type local host IP

No. 4: Click “Task” menu button and then sub-menu “Catalogue”

No. 5: Create new task by clicking “New” button. New task menu will be opened.

No.	Application	Desir. Date	Description	Category	Topology	Asset Code	Asset Description	Status	Trades
101	24/01/2017 15:06		Operators detect malfunction	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
100	24/01/2017 14:12		A malfunction happens to the	Malfunction			BIOCAT Liquid Feed Subsystem	Open	Chemical Engineer
98	24/01/2017 13:09		A malfunction happens at the	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
96	24/01/2017 12:43		Malfunction at the rooftop	Malfunction			CHU_EXT, CALIBRATION ROOM	Open	Chemical Engineer
94	24/01/2017 12:30		Malfunction at the Syngas	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
92	24/01/2017 12:20		A malfunction was detected	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
90	24/01/2017 12:06		A malfunction was detected	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Executing	Chemical Engineer
89	16/12/2016 12:06		new construction	New Construction			WING A', L307, VENT.UNIT	Open	Chemical Engineer
88	16/12/2016 12:03		malfunction	Malfunction	EKETA	testAsset	testAsset	Open	Electrical Technician
87	15/12/2016 13:27		test	Malfunction	EKETA	testAsset	testAsset	Open	Automation Technician

No. 6: Fill missing data and set up category, template task, application date, trade, department, criticality, detection, applicant, etc. Choose from a list of people who is responsible for completing the task, by name and their position (e.g. supervisor, worker or technician). Click the “Save” button.

Waiting for 54.93.88.57...

No. 7: Repeat step 4, click “Catalogue” menu and check if the task is done appropriately (*Highly Recommended*).

No. 8: Click “Task” menu in order to review the schedule with the Scheduling sub-menu. Opened and scheduled tasks are both presented.

Desir.	Date	Description	Category	Topology	Asset Code	Asset Description	Status	Trades	Select
10:00		Test the application	Preventive Maintenance		C01	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+
6:22		Missing power	Corrective action		C02	Cabinet02	Open	Mechanic	+
6:20		Short circuit	Breakdown		C01	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+

No. 9: Click on “Scheduling” to check the list of scheduled tasks

No. 10: Click first on “Task” menu and then click on button “Scheduling”.

Scheduling is completed.

No. 11: Command line will do the control check of the tasks if everything is OK. If it is OK, a new task is scheduled. If not, red error detection is pointed out.

```

The transacted install has completed.

C:\Atlantis\IDSS>idss --standalone
2017-03-09 11:46:06.359 [I] DEBUG ABE.IDSS.Program [(null)] - starting
2017-03-09 11:46:06.400 [I] INFO ABE.IDSS.KitchenSink [(null)] - Starting server at http://160.40.2.206:9070
2017-03-09 11:46:06.557 [I] ERROR idss [(null)] - Unhandled exception
System.Reflection.TargetInvocationException: Exception has been thrown by the target of an invocation. --> System.Net.HttpListenerException: Access is denied
   at System.Net.HttpListener.AddAllPrefixes()
   at System.Net.HttpListener.Start()
   at Microsoft.Owin.Host.HttpListener.OwinHttpListener.Start(HttpListener listener, Func`2 appFunc, IList`1 addresses, IDictionary`2 Properties, Func`2 loggerFactory)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Host.HttpListener.OwinServerFactory.Create(Func`2 app, IDictionary`2 properties)
   --- End of inner exception stack trace ---
   at System.RuntimeMethodHandle.InvokeMethod(Object target, Object[] arguments, Signature sig, Boolean constructor)
   at System.Reflection.RuntimeMethodInfo.UnsafeInvokeInternal(Object obj, Object[] parameters, Object[] arguments)
   at System.Reflection.RuntimeMethodInfo.Invoke(Object obj, BindingFlags invokeAttr, Binder binder, Object[] parameters, CultureInfo culture)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.ServerFactory.ServerFactoryAdapter.Create(IAppBuilder builder)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Engine.HostingEngine.StartServer(StartContext context)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Engine.HostingEngine.Start(StartContext context)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Starter.DirectHostingStarter.Start(StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Starter.HostingStarter.Start(StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.WebApp.StartImplementation(IServiceProvider services, StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.WebApp.Start(StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.WebApp.StartITStartup(StartOptions options)
   at ABE.IDSS.KitchenSink.TryLaunchServer() in C:\Users\charisi\Documents\satisfactory\Src\IDSS\Program.cs:line 161
   at ABE.IDSS.Program.Main(String[] args) in C:\Users\charisi\Documents\satisfactory\Src\IDSS\Program.cs:line 54

Unhandled Exception: System.Reflection.TargetInvocationException: Exception has been thrown by the target of an invocation. --> System.Net.HttpListenerException: Access is denied
   at System.Net.HttpListener.AddAllPrefixes()
   at System.Net.HttpListener.Start()
   at Microsoft.Owin.Host.HttpListener.OwinHttpListener.Start(HttpListener listener, Func`2 appFunc, IList`1 addresses, IDictionary`2 Properties, Func`2 loggerFactory)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Host.HttpListener.OwinServerFactory.Create(Func`2 app, IDictionary`2 properties)
   --- End of inner exception stack trace ---
   at System.RuntimeMethodHandle.InvokeMethod(Object target, Object[] arguments, Signature sig, Boolean constructor)
   at System.Reflection.RuntimeMethodInfo.UnsafeInvokeInternal(Object obj, Object[] parameters, Object[] arguments)
   at System.Reflection.RuntimeMethodInfo.Invoke(Object obj, BindingFlags invokeAttr, Binder binder, Object[] parameters, CultureInfo culture)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.ServerFactory.ServerFactoryAdapter.Create(IAppBuilder builder)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Engine.HostingEngine.StartServer(StartContext context)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Engine.HostingEngine.Start(StartContext context)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Starter.DirectHostingStarter.Start(StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.Starter.HostingStarter.Start(StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.WebApp.StartImplementation(IServiceProvider services, StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.WebApp.Start(StartOptions options)
   at Microsoft.Owin.Hosting.WebApp.StartITStartup(StartOptions options)
   at ABE.IDSS.KitchenSink.TryLaunchServer() in C:\Users\charisi\Documents\satisfactory\Src\IDSS\Program.cs:line 161
   at ABE.IDSS.Program.Main(String[] args) in C:\Users\charisi\Documents\satisfactory\Src\IDSS\Program.cs:line 54

C:\Atlantis\IDSS>

```

6.1.3.3 Scenario 3: Rebalancing Workload with HR Workload balancing Toolkit (**Supervisor**)

Steps:

No. 1: Open browser e.g. , and type local host IP <http://localhost/HomeNew/IndexNew>

No. 2: Click “Task” menu button and then sub-menu “Catalogue”

No. 3: Click “Task” menu button in order to review the schedule with the “Scheduling” sub-menu. Opened and scheduled tasks are both presented.

The 'Scheduling' sub-menu is open, displaying a table of scheduled tasks:

Desir. Date	Description	Category	Topology	Asset Code	Asset Description	Status	Trades	Select
0:00	Test the application	Preventive Maintenance		C01	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+
6:22	Missing power	Corrective action		C02	Cabinet02	Open	Mechanic	+
6:20	Short circuit	Breakdown		C01	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+

No. 4: Click on “Scheduling” to check the list of scheduled tasks

The 'Scheduling' sub-menu is open, displaying a table of scheduled tasks:

Desir. Date	Description	Category	Topology	Asset Code	Asset Description	Status	Trades	Select
0:00	Test the application	Preventive Maintenance		C01	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+
6:22	Missing power	Corrective action		C02	Cabinet02	Open	Mechanic	+
6:20	Short circuit	Breakdown		C01	Cabinet01	Open	Electrician	+

No. 5: Click first on “Task” menu and then click on button “Scheduling”.

Scheduling is completed.

Supervisor can check the program and accept the schedule automatically assigned by HR. Supervisor is able to adjust the defined schedule according to the needs of the working day/week/month by using drag and drop option within scheduling calendar.

6.1.3.4 Scenario 4: Rebalancing Workload with HR Workload balancing Toolkit (**Worker**).

Steps:

No. 1: Open browser e.g. , and type local host IP <http://localhost/HomeNew/IndexNew>

No. 2: Click first on "Task" menu and then click on button "Scheduling".

No. 3: By clicking on “Scheduling” sub – menu check the list of scheduled tasks

Scheduling is completed and worker can see and follow the scheduled tasks for the working day/week/month.

6.1.3.5 Scenario 5: Assigning Gamification to Steps for all users.

The user (i.e. administrator) is responsible to create new tasks and provide all necessary information within Maintenance toolkit and IDSS. The user, will choose the proper actor (administrator, worker or technician) in order to complete the defined action. IDSS and Maintenance toolkit must be installed on a local PC that administrator is using.

Steps:

No. 1: Run IDSS.exe application file (locally installed at users' PC).

No. 2: Type “idss- gamification” in the command line and press enter.


```

C:\Users\ainms>cd ..
C:\Users>cd ..
C:\>cd atlantis
C:\Atlantis>cd idss
C:\Atlantis\IDSS>idss --gamification
2017-06-19 14:57:01,309 [1] DEBUG ABE.IDSS.Program [(null)] - starting
Last task :141620
Total tasks:2085-last task 141620-last completed 141620
Total tasks:2085-last task 141620-last completed 141620
Total tasks:2085-last task 141620-last completed 141620
  
```


No. 3: Open browser e.g. <http://localhost/HomeNew/IndexNew> , and type local host IP

No. 4: Click “Task” menu button and then sub-menu “Catalogue”

The screenshot shows the Satisfactory web application interface. At the top, there's a navigation bar with 'Tasks', 'Warehouse', 'Preventive', 'Core data', 'Manage', and 'Help'. A sidebar menu on the left includes 'Request', 'Catalog', 'Start', 'End', 'Management', 'Scheduling', 'Work Requests', 'Reports', and 'Charts'. The main area features a 'Task Catalogue' with a search bar and a 'Quick Search' button. Below this is a line chart titled 'per month' showing task counts from 2016/08 to 2017/01. To the right, there's a 'New Tasks' table with columns for No., Application Date, Category, and Asset. Below the chart is a 'Delayed Tasks' table with columns for No., Application Date, Category, and Asset. At the bottom right, there are two performance gauges: 'Percentage of Delayed Tasks' (0.00%) and 'Percentage of Faults/Preventives' (100.00%).

No. 5: Create new task by clicking “New” button. New task menu will be opened.

The screenshot shows a detailed view of the task list in the Satisfactory application. The table has columns for No., Application, Desir. Date, Description, Category, Topology, Asset Code, Asset Description, Status, and Trades. The data includes various malfunction reports and construction tasks.

No.	Application	Desir. Date	Description	Category	Topology	Asset Code	Asset Description	Status	Trades
101	24/01/2017 15:06		Operators detect malfunction	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
100	24/01/2017 14:12		A malfunction happens to the	Malfunction			BIOCAT Liquid Feed Subsystem	Open	Chemical Engineer
98	24/01/2017 13:09		A malfunction happens at the	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
96	24/01/2017 12:43		Malfunction at the rooftop	Malfunction			CHU_EXT, CALIBRATION ROOM	Open	Chemical Engineer
94	24/01/2017 12:30		Malfunction at the Syngas	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
92	24/01/2017 12:20		A malfunction was detected	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
90	24/01/2017 12:06		A malfunction was detected	Malfunction	SYNGAS	SYNGAS-UNIT	Syngas Unit	Open	Chemical Engineer
89	16/12/2016 12:06		new construction	New Construction			WING A', L307, VENT.UNIT	Open	Chemical Engineer
88	16/12/2016 12:03		malfunction	Malfunction	EKETA	testAsset	testAsset	Open	Electrical Technician
87	15/12/2016 13:27		test	Malfunction	EKETA	testAsset	testAsset	Open	Automation Technician

No. 6: Fill missing data and set up category, template task, application date, trade, department, criticality, detection, applicant, etc. Choose from a list of people who is responsible for completing the task, by name and their position (e.g. supervisor, worker or technician). Click the “Save” button

No. 7: Repeat step 4. Then, select the proper task and click “Start” button.

No. 8: Open browser e.g. , and type account type http://160.40.51.143:40000/satisfactory_cperi/app/#!/admin/games.

No. 9: Click on My Profile/Achievements and enter the game page.

No. 1: Click on SatisFactory shortcut on the screen of the mobile phone.

No. 2: Satisfactory logo will appear (A). Click in the middle of the logo and log in with appropriate credentials (B). Click "Start" (C) button.

No. 3: The following page is displayed.

Worker can check daily schedule from the list of already defined tasks. There are Start, Refresh and Cancel buttons that a worker can use

No. 4: Select task and the task screen with task description, asset and solution information will pop out.

Worker can either click END button to finish this task, or CANCEL to abort it.

No. 5: Swipe left and continue with new task screen where we can see applicant, fault code and responsible technician for malfunction.

There are two buttons that can be used, add technician and add sub-task.

No. 6: Swipe left to check the instructions and details of the task that needs to be completed.

Worker can check the details of the required steps. Swipe left to check the instructions and the details of the task he needs to complete

No. 7: Swipe left. Screen shows that possible files (i.e. machine schema, photos, comments from other workers of possible solution) can be attached.

No. 8: Swipe right to the beginning.

Check if the task is completed and click the END button in order to finish the task and he schedule new task. Its blue together with notification.

Solution

No. 9: Task Completed Notification

After the worker has completed the task, the schedule screen is updated without the completed task and a notification with the message "Task completed!" appears on the screen.

6.1.5 VTDAT (Visual Training Data Analytics Toolkit)

6.1.5.1 Scenario 1: Training data analytics Toolkit for Administrator.

No. 1: Open browser e.g. , and type administrator IP: file:///C:/Users/charisi/Documents/vtdat/vtdat/index.html#/dashboards/dashboard_1

The following main Dashboard page will open and daily reviews, that administrator can create/edit, (i.e. data, news reports, comment and tweets, scheduled meetings) will be displayed.

Administrator can jump to Dashboard v.3 and check the progress of different working teams or individuals, scheduled training hours and training sessions that will be attended, lit with timelines of different training sessions that are currently running.

Furthermore, at the Graphs section, Training KPIs (i.e. Training Score Over time, Trainee distribution, Overview Chart Example) are presented.

The “Training Score Over Time” graph presents the progress of a trainee during a certain time period. The “Trainee distribution” pie chart shows the distribution of worker to three different levels: novice, intermediate, expert.

Finally, the “Overview Chart Example” presents the worker development from novice to intermediate and then expert, according to four different KPIs that are represented to the axes of the chart.

6.1.5.2 Scenario 2: Training Data Analytics Toolkit for Supervisor

Steps:

No. 1: Open browser e.g. , and type supervisor IP: file:///C:/Users/charisi/Documents/vtdat/vtdat/index.html#/dashboards/dashboard_3.

The following main Dashboard page will open and daily reviews that a supervisor can ONLY follow (i.e. data, news reports, comment and tweets, scheduled meetings) will be displayed.

Furthermore, Supervisor can check the Graphs section, Training KPIs (i.e. Training Score Over time, Trainee distribution, Overview Chart Example) are presented.

The graphs and charts are the same with the ones the administrators see, because both the administrator and the supervisor participate in the decision making process.

6.1.5.3 Scenario 3: Training data analytics Toolkit for Worker

Steps:

No. 1: Open browser e.g. , and type worker IP: file:///C:/Users/charisi/Documents/vtadat/vtadat/index.html#/charts/chartist_chart.

The following Chart list will open, containing information and different data regarding training distribution (per day/week/quartile). Furthermore, the Pie and Gauge charts presents new KPIs, that have already been approved by Administrator and Supervisor. This is ongoing work.

6.1.6 Localization Manager (UWB Wearables)

6.1.6.1 Scenario1: Typical Application

In this example there will be a person walking around the SUNLIGHT shop floor, in the localization area, with the UWB-WD in his hand. The pictures presented in the example will show two different kind of information: the main picture (identified with 1) will show the person walking in the real scenario, while a secondary picture (identified with 2) will show in real-time the position of the person in the map. It is worth mentioning that picture 2 is the UI presented by the toolkit component which will not be presented in this tutorial. In addition, the toolkit UI is supervised by the managers to get every important shop floor event.

- **Step 1:** The worker is moving around his working space (Figure 153).
- **Step 2:** At a certain point the worker enters in the dangerous area without noticing it (Figure 154).
- **Step 3:** The manager receives a visual alarm, in the toolkit, from the UWB-WD associated to the worker indicating he is in the dangerous area.
- **Step 4:** The manager informs the worker about the dangerous situation.
- **Step 5:** The worker puts himself in a safe position.
- **Step 6:** The manager receives the notification, from the UWB-WD associated to the worker, that there is not dangerous situation anymore.

Figure 153: Person walking around the shop floor.

Figure 154: Person entered in dangerous zone.

Figure 155: Person exit from dangerous zone.

6.1.7 AR Glasses

6.1.7.1 Scenario 1: In-factory training and support of workers using a flexible learning platform

The use of the AR Glasses of GlassUp on training and support applications on the shopfloor utilizes the same toolset of the AROP Training Platform but instead of presenting the information on a Tablet or a Desktop PC, the information is presented on the AR Glasses. The tablet is however used to load a procedure and to navigate between steps and descriptive layers.

Hence, the initial **4 steps** of this scenario are the same as the ones on 6.1.2.1.

Once a procedure (that was exported in the AROP Creation Tool with GlassUp support) is loaded, the Descriptive Layers of each step are transmitted via the GlassUp API to the glasses.

In order to navigate between **Next** and **Previous** action, as well as to load different Descriptive Layers there are two different input options:

- Using the external control base
- Using the Gesture Control Manager

Here we will describe the steps involved using the Gesture Control Manager

In order for the user to navigate the actions, the Left and Right swipe are used in the same way as described in 6.1.7.1 while cycling between different Descriptive Layers is performed by lifting both hands up as described in the same scenario.

6.1.7.2 Scenario 2: Monitoring and online notification of abnormal events or alarms

The use of the AR glasses for Monitoring and online identification is a passive operation that depends solely on the back-end notification system and as such there are no steps involved for the end user other than wearing the AR Glasses.

6.1.7.3 Scenario 3: Remote assistance (Worker)

Figure 156 Indicative sequence of actions in a remote assistance session

The steps that are followed in a typical remote assistance scenario are described next.

Step 1: Request assistance: Initially, the worker that is facing a problem makes a request for assistance to the appropriate supervisor via the social collaboration platform using a mobile device (tablet or smartphone). The notification engine of the social collaboration platform dispatches a notification event to the supervisor.

Step 2: After the worker has reviewed the provided information that had been sent by the supervisor, the worker can then provide feedback to the supervisor via the notification engine, by selecting the appropriate response, among a list of pre-defined responses, regarding the assistance provided (e.g. OK, Repeat, More information requested).

Step 3: Lastly, in case the worker has a request or question, it is possible to send instant text messages to the supervisor by using the respective functionality of the social collaboration platform through a mobile device.

6.1.7.4 Scenario 4: Remote assistance (Supervisor)

Step 1: View video stream from glasses. As soon as the supervisor accepts a request from the worker, he can select the desired actions for initiating the assistance session. For instance, there is an option for the supervisor to start the video stream of the AR Glasses built-in camera. Therefore, in this case, the supervisor is able to view the real-time video stream of the AR Glasses built-in camera, in order to evaluate the situation and diagnose the issue, as shown in the following figure.

Figure 157 Supervisor viewing real-time video stream from worker's AR Glasses through Social Collaboration Platform

Step 2: Send voice instructions. Additionally, the supervisor can send voice instructions to the remote worker as well as instructions via text messages that will be displayed on the worker's AR Glasses device.

Figure 158 Supervisor sending instructions as text messages to the worker's AR Glasses

Step 3: Send images. Manuals or schematics can also be sent by the supervisor to the worker's AR Glasses as images in order to indicate the correct procedure or status of the equipment to the worker, helping resolve a malfunction.

Figure 159 Supervisor sending schematics and text to indicate the correct procedure to the worker

Step 4: Real-time playback of video or audio streams on the AR Glasses is also supported. The supervisor can initiate a local video or audio RTSP stream through the social collaboration platform. The social collaboration platform then sends a request to the AR Glasses which contains the URI of the RTSP server. Then, the AR Glasses connect to the RTSP server and the stream is played on the device.

6.1.8 Suggestions Platform

6.1.8.1 Scenario 1: Using the Suggestions Platform

Step 1: Click on suggestions tab to see the new ideas suggested and their progress

CATEGORIES	SUGGESTIONS			
Production Process Improvement	an anonymou... 3 months ago 2 votes	This is yet an... 3 months ago 0 votes	Testing 5 months ago 1 votes	test2 7 months ago 1 votes
Equipment and Facilities	Έγχρωμος εκ... 21 days ago 1 votes	Muffle furnace a month ago 2 votes	Εκτυπωτής σ... 2 months ago -1 votes	Αναβάθμιση ... 2 months ago 5 votes
Human Resources	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago -1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 0 votes	Christmas bo ... 7 months ago 1 votes	Overtime pay ... 10 months ago 1 votes
Existing Product Improvement	Testing 5 months ago 0 votes			
New Product Ideas	Παρακολούθη... 4 months ago 0 votes	Mobile app fo... 7 months ago 1 votes	Extend the u... 7 months ago 1 votes	Biodiesel 2nd... 10 months ago 0 votes
Health and Safety	Ασκήσεις εκκ... 2 months ago 4 votes	Κανόνες ασφ... 2 months ago 1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 1 votes	Safety equip... 3 months ago -2 votes
Miscellaneous	Αγορά εργαλε... 2 months ago 0 votes	Εκδρομή Εξέτ... 2 months ago -2 votes	Recycle bins ... 10 months ago 3 votes	

Step 2: Click on suggest button to make a new suggestion

Step 3: Add title and text for the suggestion and choose category for uploading

< Suggestions

Make a suggestion

This suggestion is **NOT** anonymous.
By submitting you will also submit your username (Platform Administrator). If you do not wish to do so, please log out.

Title

Describe your suggestion

CHOOSE CATEGORY

Step 4: Type a character or words to the search text box in order to filter the suggestions shown.

SUGGEST

Show: **ACCEPTED** MODIFIED REJECTED PENDING

Categories: SUGGESTIONS

CATEGORIES	SUGGESTIONS
Production Process Improvement	<div>an anonymou... 2 votes 3 months ago</div> <div>This is yet an... 0 votes 3 months ago</div>
Equipment and Facilities	<div>an anonymou... 0 votes 3 months ago</div>
Human Resources	No suggestions in this category
Existing Product Improvement	No suggestions in this category
New Product Ideas	No suggestions in this category
Health and Safety	No suggestions in this category
Miscellaneous	No suggestions in this category

Step 5: For filtering, the users can click or unclick the choices of accepted-modified-rejected and pending tags.

CATEGORIES	SUGGESTIONS				
Production Process Improvement	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>This is yet an... 3 months ago 0 votes</td> <td>Testing 5 months ago 1 votes</td> <td>test2 7 months ago 1 votes</td> <td>Test 7 months ago 2 votes</td> </tr> </table>	This is yet an... 3 months ago 0 votes	Testing 5 months ago 1 votes	test2 7 months ago 1 votes	Test 7 months ago 2 votes
This is yet an... 3 months ago 0 votes	Testing 5 months ago 1 votes	test2 7 months ago 1 votes	Test 7 months ago 2 votes		
Equipment and Facilities	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Έγχρωμος εκ... 21 days ago 1 votes</td> <td>Muffle furnace a month ago 2 votes</td> <td>Εκριτωτής σ... 2 months ago -1 votes</td> <td>Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 1 votes</td> </tr> </table>	Έγχρωμος εκ... 21 days ago 1 votes	Muffle furnace a month ago 2 votes	Εκριτωτής σ... 2 months ago -1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 1 votes
Έγχρωμος εκ... 21 days ago 1 votes	Muffle furnace a month ago 2 votes	Εκριτωτής σ... 2 months ago -1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 1 votes		
Human Resources	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago -1 votes</td> <td>Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 0 votes</td> <td>Christmas bo... 7 months ago 1 votes</td> <td>Overtime pay... 10 months ago 1 votes</td> </tr> </table>	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago -1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 0 votes	Christmas bo... 7 months ago 1 votes	Overtime pay... 10 months ago 1 votes
Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago -1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 0 votes	Christmas bo... 7 months ago 1 votes	Overtime pay... 10 months ago 1 votes		
Existing Product Improvement	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Testing 5 months ago 0 votes</td> <td></td> <td></td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Testing 5 months ago 0 votes			
Testing 5 months ago 0 votes					
New Product Ideas	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Παρακολούθη... a month ago 0 votes</td> <td>Mobile app fo... 7 months ago 1 votes</td> <td>Extend the u... 7 months ago 1 votes</td> <td>Biodiesel 2nd... 10 months ago 0 votes</td> </tr> </table>	Παρακολούθη... a month ago 0 votes	Mobile app fo... 7 months ago 1 votes	Extend the u... 7 months ago 1 votes	Biodiesel 2nd... 10 months ago 0 votes
Παρακολούθη... a month ago 0 votes	Mobile app fo... 7 months ago 1 votes	Extend the u... 7 months ago 1 votes	Biodiesel 2nd... 10 months ago 0 votes		
Health and Safety	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Ασκήσεις εκκ... 2 months ago 4 votes</td> <td>Κανόνες ασφ... 2 months ago 1 votes</td> <td>Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 1 votes</td> <td>Safety equip... 3 months ago -2 votes</td> </tr> </table>	Ασκήσεις εκκ... 2 months ago 4 votes	Κανόνες ασφ... 2 months ago 1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 1 votes	Safety equip... 3 months ago -2 votes
Ασκήσεις εκκ... 2 months ago 4 votes	Κανόνες ασφ... 2 months ago 1 votes	Πρόταση για ... 2 months ago 1 votes	Safety equip... 3 months ago -2 votes		
Miscellaneous	<table border="1"> <tr> <td>Αγορά εργαλ... 2 months ago 0 votes</td> <td>Εκδρομή Εκτ... 2 months ago -2 votes</td> <td>Recycle bins ... 10 months ago 3 votes</td> <td></td> </tr> </table>	Αγορά εργαλ... 2 months ago 0 votes	Εκδρομή Εκτ... 2 months ago -2 votes	Recycle bins ... 10 months ago 3 votes	
Αγορά εργαλ... 2 months ago 0 votes	Εκδρομή Εκτ... 2 months ago -2 votes	Recycle bins ... 10 months ago 3 votes			

6.1.8.2 Scenario 2: Adding a suggestion

To add a suggestion, click the “Suggest”-button to get to the “Add Suggestion View”. Here you have to enter a title and short description of your suggestion. The suggestion will not be anonymous if the user is logged in. If you do not wish to do so, log out or use the suggestion kiosk.

Make a suggestion

This suggestion is NOT anonymous. By submitting you will also submit your username (Rena Lithoxidou). If you do not wish to do so, please log out .

Test

This is a test

CHOOSE CATEGORY

After the user will have to choose a category for your suggestion.

Choose category

Production Process Improvement
Suggestions concerning the production line, the schedule and the resources involved in the production process

Equipment and Facilities
Improvements related to workplace facilities and equipment.

Human Resources
Improvements addressing organizational or contractual issues and company's culture.

Existing Product Improvement
Your ideas for improving existing products.

New Product Ideas
Your ideas for new products.

Miscellaneous
Ideas related to any other topic

SUBMIT SUGGESTION **BACK**

6.1.8.3 Scenario 3: Manager Functions

Management functions are available to managers of a specific category only. If the user is not in charge of a category, the user will not see the buttons for management functionalities.

6.1.8.3.1 Changing a suggestions status

We would like to have more possibilities to share our experiences and what we learned from these experiences. In this way other workers can learn from others mistakes and also can improve themselves.

December 20 2016, 7:00 am

-3
votes

PENDING

Moderator

 John Papas
lu_life@satisfactory.com

Collaborators

Invite collaborators

Search for user

ACCEPT **MODIFY** **REJECT**

In order to change a suggestions status, go to the detail view and scroll to the bottom. There the user will find buttons to accept, modify or reject a suggestion. If you want to modify a suggestion, after clicking “Modify” the user will be prompted to enter the modifications. After you have entered them, click “Modify” again and the status will be saved.

A screenshot of a web interface for a moderator. At the top, it says "Moderator" and shows a profile for "John Papas" with the email "lu_life@satisfactory.com". Below this is a section for "Collaborators" with a sub-heading "Invite collaborators" and a search bar labeled "Search for user". The main section is titled "Modify suggestion" with a "Cancel" link. Below the title, there is a text input field containing the text "This is my modification". At the bottom, there are three buttons: "ACCEPT" (grey), "MODIFY" (yellow), and "REJECT" (grey).

If you want to reject a suggestion, after clicking “Reject” the user will be prompted to enter a reason for rejecting this suggestion. After you have entered them, click “Reject” again and the status will be saved.

A screenshot of a web interface for a moderator, similar to the previous one. It shows the same moderator profile and collaborator section. The main section is titled "Reject suggestion" with a "Cancel" link. Below the title, there is a text input field containing the text "My reason is". At the bottom, there are three buttons: "ACCEPT" (grey), "MODIFY" (grey), and "REJECT" (red).

6.1.8.3.2 Inviting a collaborator

The user can add other managers as collaborators to a specific suggestion. To do this got the detail view of a specific suggestion. Under “Invite collaborators” the user will find a search box to search for the user you want to add. If you have found the user, click on “Invite”. An invite will be sent to the user, if the user accepts the invite the user will become collaborator and have the right to change the suggestions status.

6.1.8.4 Scenario 4: Handling Collaboration requests

The user can see an overview of open collaboration requests you have received and open invites you have sent to other collaborators. To access this view click on “collaboration requests” in the overview.

6.1.8.4.1 Open Invitations

These are collaboration invitations sent to you by other managers. The user can accept and reject them right in this view. To go to the specific suggestion, the user can click on the suggestion title.

[< Suggestions](#)

OPEN INVITATIONS PENDING REQUESTS

FROM	SUGGESTION		
John Papas	Getting More Feedback	ACCEPT	REJECT
John Papas	Sharing Experiences with others	ACCEPT	REJECT

6.1.8.4.2 Pending Requests

To see invitations you have sent to other managers but that were not accepted or rejected, click on “Pending Requests”. If you have changed your mind about one of these requests, the user can retract your invitation thus deleting the request.

[< Suggestions](#)

OPEN INVITATIONS PENDING REQUESTS

TO	SUGGESTION	
Dimitris Trigkas	Getting More Feedback	RETRACT INVITE
Demo Satisfactory	Getting More Feedback	RETRACT INVITE
Demo Satisfactory	Sharing Experiences with others	RETRACT INVITE

6.1.8.4.3 Adding a category

Click on “Add category” in the Overview. The user will be able to add to a maximum of nine categories. More categories are blocked in order to not overwhelm the users using the kiosk.

COLLABORATION REQUESTS **SUGGEST** Show: **ACCEPTED** **MODIFIED** **REJECTED** **PENDING** Search

CATEGORIES SUGGESTIONS

Production Process Improvement	Visualizatio... 2 votes 10 days ago	Digital man... 10 votes 4 months ago	VR Training... 2 votes 6 months ago	Improve the... 0 votes a year ago
Equipment and Facilities	Canteen O... 4 votes 10 days ago	More Comf... 22 votes 8 months ago		
Human Resources	Getting Mor... 15 votes 16 days ago	Sharing Ex... -3 votes 5 months ago	Digital Vaca... 0 votes 7 months ago	
Existing Product Improvement	No suggestions in this category			
New Product Ideas	No suggestions in this category			
Miscellaneous	Veggies in t... 4 votes 8 minutes ago			

[+ Add Category](#) Click to add a new category

After clicking on “Add category” the user will have to add a title, a description and a manager who will be responsible for this category’s suggestions. For choosing a manager you have a search box where the user can search all collaboration platform users. The “Save”-Button will be disabled until you enter all the necessary information.

[< Suggestions](#)

Add Category

Title

Please, provide a short description for this category

Assign a manager to this category:

Search for user

SAVE

6.1.8.4.4 Editing a category

If the user is a manager assigned to a category, the user can edit this categories title and description. The user can also assign a different manager to this category. If the category already contains suggestions, please bear in mind that when editing the title and description you might take those suggestions out of context.

6.1.8.4.5 Deleting a category

Click on “Delete” for the specific category. The user will be prompted to confirm the deletion of a category and all its suggestions.

After confirming this prompt the category will be permanently deleted.

6.1.9 Digital Andon/Gesture control

6.1.9.1 Scenario 1: Instructions browsing

The Digital Andon St module allows the Smart Assembly Station operator to browse a set of assembly instructions. The visualization of the next instruction is triggered by the gesture “right hand swipe to left” depicted in Figure 160.

Figure 160: Right hand swipe left gesture

After the gesture the interface will show the next instruction of the set with a slide from right animation (Figure 161). The browsing progress on the top right of the screen will be updated accordingly (e.g. instruction 9/10). When the last instruction is reached any further “right hand swipe to left” gestures are ignored.

This behaviour is the same for both standard and directory mode but the latter will also show the navigation tree (Figure 161) which display the current navigation status.

Figure 161: Next instruction animation

Symmetrically, “left hand swipe to right” gesture (Figure 162) navigates to the previous instructions.

Figure 162: Left hand swipe right gesture

When directory mode is enabled, each subdirectory is represented by a special icon as showed in Figure 163.

Figure 163: Directory icon

This icon indicate that the subdirectory can be expanded using the gesture “both hand raised over the head” gesture (Figure 164) to access nested files.

Figure 164: Both hands raised over the head gesture

Figure 165 shows interface changes before (left) and after (right) the gesture. After the gesture the first instruction nested inside the directory is displayed and the operator can browse the contents to locate the required instruction using the previously described swipe gestures.

Figure 165: Directory browsing

If the gesture is issued on a tree leaf both the interface and the navigation tree are reset to the initial status.

In standard mode, the “both hand raised over the head” gesture allows to switch between the standard and the assistance instructions. When this switching is detected, the number of current instruction in the standard set is bookmarked so that when returning back to the standard mode the browsing progress is preserved. Furthermore once the assistance set is displayed, repeating the both-hand-raised gesture toggles back to standard set.

Invalid or corrupted files formats are displayed with the following icon:

Figure 166: Corrupted file icon

6.1.9.2 Scenario 2: Audio call controls

The two gestures described in this section allow the Smart Assembly Station operator to make or receive audio calls from their supervisors. Gestures meaning is the same for both the working modes described above.

The icon on the top-right corner of the interface provides feedback on the state of the audio service. The following table describes the meaning of each of the available icon :

Icon	Description
	The audio service is not available or proper audio devices (e.g. microphone) are missing

	<p>This icon indicates that the audio service is working correctly</p>
	<p>This icon meaning is twofold. A shaking icon means that the Digital Andon St is receiving a new incoming call. On the other hand, a pulsating icon means that a call is ongoing.</p>

When the audio service is active, the operator can issue an audio communication request using the gesture depicted below:

Figure 167: right arm raised and left arm point out gesture

If the supervisor is unreachable or rejects the call a message will be shown to describe the problem occurred. The symmetrical gesture (Figure 168) can be used by the operator to terminate the call.

Figure 168: left arm raised and right arm point out gesture

When an incoming call request is received an additional message is displayed as shown below.

Figure 169: Incoming call

The operator can either accept the call with gesture in Figure 167 or reject it with gesture in Figure 168. After 30 seconds the call is automatically rejected.

6.1.10 Social Collaboration Platform

6.1.10.1 Scenario 1: User Registration and Initial Login

- Step 1: Register to the platform by clicking on the register button

- Step 2: Complete the form

- Step 3: Choose the appropriate employee category

- Step4: After registering, login to the platform by completing your email and password and clicking on login button.

A login form with two input fields. The first field is labeled "email" and has an envelope icon to its left. The second field is labeled "password" and has a lock icon to its left. Below the fields is a prominent orange "LOGIN" button.

- Step 5: Click on exclamation mark to get latest notifications of incidents

- Step 6: Click on the star to see the achievements fulfilled and what one has gained (blue circle).
- Step 7: Click on the pair of people to see pending requests for connection (green circle).
- Step 8: Click on the callout symbol to check new and old messages received (red circle).
- Step 9: Click on the bell symbol to check general notifications (orange circle).
- Step 10: Click on the planet symbol to change language – Greek and English are so far available (purple circle).

6.1.10.2 Scenario 2: Working on the Home Page

- Step 1: Click on Home button to see latest activities of colleagues that you are connected.

- Step 2: Click on call out symbol to post a text message

The 'Post text' dialog box is shown with an orange header and a close button (X). It contains the following fields:

- Title:** A text input field.
- Body:** A larger text input area.
- Privacy:** A dropdown menu currently set to 'Public'.
- POST:** A button at the bottom right to submit the post.

- Step 3: Click on the play symbol to post a video

The screenshot shows a modal window titled "Add a Video" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The form has two tabs: "INSERT YOUTUBE LINK" (selected) and "UPLOAD TO YOUTUBE". Below the tabs are input fields for "Video URL *", "Title *", and "Description". There is a "Users tagging" section with a dropdown menu showing "Platform Administrator" and a text input field for "...type a name". A "Privacy *" dropdown menu is set to "Public". At the bottom, there is a checkbox for "I have read and agree with the terms of use." and a "POST VIDEO" button.

- Step4: Click on the photo camera symbol to post a photograph

The screenshot shows a modal window titled "Add a Photo" with a close button (X) in the top right corner. The form has a "CHOOSE PHOTO TO UPLOAD" button and an "Image file *" input field. Below this are input fields for "Title" and "Users tagging" (with a dropdown menu showing "Platform Administrator" and a text input field for "...type a name"). A "Privacy *" dropdown menu is set to "Public". At the bottom, there is a "POST PHOTO" button.

6.1.10.3 Scenario 3: Networking with other users

- Step 1: Click on Network button to see all colleagues that are registered in the platform
 - Step2: Type character or the name of the colleague in the search text box for faster results.

- Step 3: Make a request to a colleague by clicking on the pair symbol of the contact.

6.1.10.4 Scenario 4: Uploading Multimedia

- Step 1: Click on Multimedia button to upload video/image context or to search between the existing ones

- Step 2: Hover on an existing multimedia file and see information about it.

- Step 3: Hover on an existing multimedia file and click on the pencil symbol to edit it, if it was uploaded from the logged in user.

6.1.10.5 Scenario 5: Using the Tips & Tricks section

Step 1: Click on Tips&Tricks button to load questions and answers from colleagues

Step 2: Click on questions tab to see what is already asked and answered

Step 3: Click on Topic to choose category of the Question

Step 4: Choose from dropdown a filter for the questions

Step 5: Type on search text box a character or words that are contained in the question.

Step 6: Click on Ask a question Tab and fill the form with the question you want to ask.

Step 7: Choose category for the question and if you want you can attach extra content by clicking the attach symbol.

Step 8: Click on My Activity tab to see the user's asked questions and given answers.

Step 9: For administrators of the platform, click on tab Topics to add or delete a topic for questions and answers.

6.1.10.6 Scenario 6: Accessing “My Profile”

Step 1: Click on My Profile tab to see the personal activity and information of the user

Step 2: Click on Action Wall tile to see the latest actions the user has made.

Step 3: Like/Share/Tag existing actions

Step 4: Click on Personal tile to see personal information about the user, the user can edit this information as well

Step 5: Change nationality

Step 6: Click on connections tile to see the user's connections

Step 7: Click on Timeline tile to move to the home page

Step 8: Click on achievements tile to see the available games, the gained points for each game the user has joined are shown in Status

Step 9: Click on Awards to view the badges won

Step 9: Click on Challenges to view the pending quests

Platform Administrator
Automation Technician

13753 points

Level 6

- Complete training session
- Find an idea for project x.
 - Brainstorming
 - Grouping ideas
 - Discussion
 - Write and send final idea

Timeline

- Status
- Awards
- Challenges
- In the crowd

Step 10 : Click on In the Crowd to view the total ranking in games

Platform Administrator
Automation Technician

Games
Suggestions app

1.	Rena Lithoxidou	47 points	
2.	Akis Kakabegas	10 points	
3.	Stella Bezergianni	8 points	
4.	Platform Administrator	4 points	
5.	Kostas Kalogiannis	4 points	
6.	Nikos Georgiou	4 points	
7.	Nikos Georgiou	4 points	
8.	Vaso Dagonikou	2 points	
9.	Chrysa Zilogou	1 points	

Timeline

- Status
- Awards
- Challenges
- In the crowd

6.1.10.7 Scenario 7: Modify Profile Settings

Step 1: Click on the personal avatar to reach settings of the profile

Step 2: Check and choose the appropriate settings for your personal profile.

Step 3: Modify settings for Account

Step 3: Modify settings for privacy

search...

SATISFACTORY ADMIN HOME NETWORK MULTIMEDIA TIPS & TRICKS SUGGESTIONS MY PROFILE

Account Privacy **Notifications**

Privacy

Change your security and privacy settings SAVE CHANGES

Photo and Video Tagging Allow anyone to tag me in photos and videos	Coworker Requests Accept requests from anyone
Messages Accept messages only from my coworkers	Post privacy Share my posts with anyone
Discoverability Status Available	Timeline Protection Allow posts from anyone
Personal Email Allow only my coworkers to see my email address	Personal Address Allow only my coworkers to see my address
Personal Phone Number Allow only my coworkers to see my phone number	

Blocking
...type a name

SAVE CHANGES

Step 3: Modify settings for Notifications

search...

SATISFACTORY ADMIN HOME NETWORK MULTIMEDIA TIPS & TRICKS SUGGESTIONS MY PROFILE

Notifications

Change your notification settings SAVE CHANGES

Others comment on my post <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification	Others like my post <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification
Others comment on a post I commented on <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification	Others tag me on a photo <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification
Others tag me on a video <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification	Others share content with me <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification
New Follower <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification	New Message <input type="checkbox"/> Email me
Others accept my coworker invitation <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification	Others share my content <input type="checkbox"/> Email me <input checked="" type="checkbox"/> In-site notification
Activate me in posting more content	Others like my comment

6.1.11 Gamification Platform Administration

6.1.11.1 Scenario 1: Gamifying a Process

Step1: Start by registering to the gamification platform. (as shown in the Social Collaboration Platform training scenarios)

User can register exclusively as specific category provided from the Platform and denote level of experience concerning the platform's usage.

A screenshot of a web registration form titled "Register". The form has an orange header bar with a close button (X). The fields include: "First name *", "Last name *", "Email *", "Password *", "Gender" (with a radio button selected for "Male"), "Type" (a dropdown menu set to "Floor Manager"), "Qualification" (a dropdown menu set to "Novice"), "Job description *", and "Birthday" (a date picker set to "23/03/2017"). At the bottom, there are two buttons: "CANCEL" and "REGISTER".

Step 2: Login to the platform

A screenshot of the Satisfactory login page. It features the Satisfactory logo and the text "Social Collaboration Platform". There are two buttons: "REGISTER" and "SUGGESTIONS". Below these, there are input fields for "email *" (with the value "admin@satisfactory.com") and "password *". A "LOGIN" button is positioned below the password field. A globe icon is visible in the top right corner.

Step 3: Click on the “Teams” tab and press the cross shape on the top right corner

Step 4: Add Team name and Team description

Create A Team

CANCEL ✕
CREATE ✓

Step 5: See the existing teams

Step 6: Click on the “Games” tab and then on the cross shape to add game

Step 7: Add Game title and Game description and choose if it is a game for team playing or single playing

Step 8: Add Action Title and Action description as well as the add or subtract choice for supportive or not awarding

Step 9: After creating at least one action, create a quest by modifying the action.

Step 10: Create an award of type Scalar (Type 1)

Step 11: Add Award Title and Award Description

Step 12: Add the amount of scalars that this awards gives

Step 13: Create an award of type Set (Type 2)

Step 14: View the created awards

In order to set a tangible object for award the process is the same as type 2.

Step 15: Set levels

In level's form the administrator can write a hint in order to help with the acquisition of it.

Step 16: Create Rule of type 1

- Add Rule name and description
- Choose if it concerns specific category of people
- Choose action
- Choose operator
- Choose times of fulfilment

- Choose gained award

Step 17: Create Rule of type 2

- Add Rule name and description
- Choose if it concerns specific category of people
- Choose how many points the user should have to gain an item of a set
- Choose operator
- Choose gained item of set

6.1.11.2 Scenario 2: Manage game operations

Step 1: Click on leaderboards to see the participants and their scores

Step 2: Click on participants to see who has joined the game

7. CONCLUSIONS

This document is about the description of the achievements of the Task 6.4, which aims to develop the training material, and VR-enabled training scenarios that will acquaint the personnel of factories with the novel solutions and tools provided by SatisFactory.

The aim of this deliverable was to present the methodology behind the selection of the SatisFactory tools to be covered by the training scenarios, the targeted users for the scenarios as well as the training use cases involved, the presentation of the training tools to be used in the deployment of these scenarios, the generation of the training material that describes the core functionalities of each tool and the final development of the training scenarios based on the material gathered.

Through the course of Task 6.4, 11 of the tools of SatisFactory were identified as end-user oriented. For these 11 tools, instructions on the core functionalities were written by the developers of each one, accompanied by screenshots, videos, screencasts and demonstrations. All the material gathered for each tool was edited, processed, cut into segments representing individual steps and combined with textual instructions in order to create step-by-step instructions on the key use cases of using these tools in everyday operations.

The resulting 31 training scenarios were then reconstructed in the AROP Creation Tool assigning multimedia material to all steps involved, defining the relations between each step and action and in some of the scenarios where it was applicable 3D VR Animated presentations of the operations depicted in some steps were also modeled, animated and incorporated into the Descriptive layers of the training scenario.

The result of the work carried out in Task T6.4 and reported in this deliverable is the final training procedures deployed to the pilot sites of COMAU, Sunlight and CPERI, where using the AROP Training Presentation tool on mobile devices, through the course of T6.3.3 a set of training sessions will be organized and implemented.